

D6.3 Gaps and Opportunities Assessment

Knowledge transfer through training – including DIRECTED Exploitation Strategy

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Report overview

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List of abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
API	Application Programming Interface
CCA	Climate Change Adaptation
CPD	Continual Professional Development
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
DRM	Disaster Risk Reduction
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
GIS	Geographic Information System
KER	Key Exploitable Results
KTP	Knowledge Transfer Plan
KT	Knowledge Transfer
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
RWL	Real World Lab
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This Deliverable D6.3 presents the Gaps and Opportunities Assessment to support knowledge transfer through training. This deliverable is generated from activities in Task 6.3 which focuses on identifying current institutional capacity for integrated multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation (M2-9) and involves 1) defining impact pathways for Key Exploitable Results (KER), 2) identifying end-users and 3) developing a custom knowledge transfer plan (message, medium, channel, impact measurement) per KER to maximise uptake/ application through training. The Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) results from an assessment of existing training and education gaps and opportunities, and benchmarking them against other programmes in Europe that support multi-hazard risk management and Climate Change Adaptation. The assessment involved a scoping survey with consortium members, a desktop review, key informant discussions and analysis of Real World Lab emerging insights supported by bilateral exchange with RWL hosts.

The Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric with its individual and interconnected tools were identified as the KER to embed within knowledge transfer and training activities in the e-Learning platform. The priority end-users identified include 1) DRM and CCA professionals with basic/varied technical knowledge (e.g. planners or coordinators in municipalities, first responders, water boards, civil protection) who can use the Risk-Tandem Framework and its interconnected technical tools in a simple way, and 2) specialised technical professionals (or Data Stewards) in DRM or CCA organisations and Real World Labs (e.g. Geographic Information System (GIS) specialists in municipalities) who can embed and operate the Data Fabric. Opportunities for an additional user-group 3) (early career) researchers/ scientists in universities or institutes will be exploited where they emerge.

This deliverable acts as input to guide Task 6.4 which is developing training programmes to support integrated responses to multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation. This involves a co-design process with priority end-users to ensure that trainers are actively involved in the development and testing of learning resources for different end users that will be made available through an identified e-Learning portal (D6.4, due Month 45). The impact pathway will involve engagement with potential and actual users to monitor the potential impact of the knowledge transfer and training activities (Task 6.5) to develop recommendations on the capacity and skills development for DRM/ CCA (D6.9, due Month 36). The deliverable is informed by the Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2) and will connect with and amplify the activities in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) and Business Development Plan (D6.5).

Table of contents

Report overview	2
Document history	3
List of abbreviations	4
Executive summary	5
Table of contents	6
Table of figures	8
Index of tables	9
1 Introduction	10
2 Methodology	16
2.1 Objective	16
2.2 Approach	16
3. Existing training and learning opportunities in DRM & CCA	18
3.1 e-Learning courses or modules	19
3.2 Online guides for governance and technical support	27
3.3. Communities of practice	31
3.4 Tailored and targeted support on-demand	35
3.5 Education/ CPD programmes	37
4 Knowledge Gaps and Training Needs	39
4.1 Transdisciplinary collaboration	40
4.2 Integrated planning DRM and CCA	42
4.3 Citizen engagement and risk communication	44
4.4 Interoperable information and communication systems	46
4.5 Integrating open source/ access knowledge	50
4.6 Multi-risk uncertainty & interpretation	51
5 Knowledge Transfer Plan	53
5.1 DRM/ CCA professionals	54

5.2 Technical specialist / Data Steward	56
5.3 (Early career) researchers and scientists.....	58
6 Towards Exploitation and Impact	60
6.1 Training supporting DIRECTED Impact	60
6.2 Exploitation / Business development roadmap	62
7 Conclusion	70
References	71
Annex 1: Survey Questions.....	78
Annex 2: Selected overview of projects with potential for collaboration	89
Annex 3: Selected overview of e-Learning platforms considered for DIRECTED	91
Partners	93

Table of figures

Figure 1: Conceptual framing of the DIRECTED project.....	10
Figure 2: Overview of the DIRECTED Real World Labs in Europe with their specific DRM/CCA challenges	11
Figure 3: Knowledge transfer potential within DIRECTED	13
Figure 4: Real World Lab host preferences for learning approaches.....	19
Figure 5: Network of DIRECTED consortium members and partner projects	35
Figure 6: Main knowledge gaps interoperability in DRM and CCA addressed by DIRECTED	39
Figure 7: The Climate Connectivity Hub	47
Figure 8: An example of a taxonomy concept in the Climate Connectivity Hub with definition, synonyms and scope notes.....	49
Figure 9: Exploitation process and linked deliverables	65
Figure 10: Two-Tier Business Development Strategies.....	67
Figure 11: Timeline of Exploitation work in the DIRECTED Project	69

Index of tables

Table 1: Types of Knowledge Transfer activities or mechanisms	12
Table 2: e-Learning modules/ courses available related to risk management and climate adaptation	21
Table 3: List of online interactive tools available targeting practitioners working on DRM/ CCA	29
Table 4: Identified communities of practice, forums or networks supporting knowledge exchange, training and learning around multi-risk management and climate adaptation	32
Table 5: Expected outcomes and outputs linked to Knowledge Transfer Plan.....	61
Table 6: Climate Risk and Adaptation Tools and Models under adjustment in the DIRECTED Project.	63

1 Introduction

1.1 Knowledge transfer in the DIRECTED context

The DIRECTED project is supporting transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes and developing an innovative digital architecture for process integration and analytics to enhance and integrate Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) across Europe. DIRECTED will facilitate enhanced knowledge-based dialogue, communication, cooperation, and “interoperability” on the three levels that are essential to the planning management, and adaptation to extreme climate events in a multi-scale and multi-risk perspective: 1) Governance interoperability, 2) Information interoperability, and 3) Data and model interoperability (Figure 1.). Central to DIRECTED, and its knowledge transfer, are four Real World Labs (RWL) coordinated by local DRM/ CCA practitioners: RWL 1 the Capital Region of Denmark surrounding Copenhagen; RWL 2 Emilia-Romagna Region in Italy; RWL 3 the Danube Region with local focus areas on Vienna, Austria and the Zala Region in Hungary; and, RWL 4 the Rhine-Erft Region in the west of Germany. Together with stakeholders in the RWLs, DIRECTED is co-developing and testing the **Risk-Tandem Framework** and the **Data Fabric** (see more in Section 1.2) and will demonstrate their benefits for more integrated disaster/ climate risk governance and interoperable technical (data/ modelling) systems.

Figure 1: Conceptual framing of the DIRECTED project.

DIRECTED is a **transdisciplinary project** that aims to bridge science and practice, by integrating different sources of knowledge, data models and tools, accounting for different views and values of stakeholders through co-production while collaboratively finding solutions to societal challenges around risk and resilience. Knowledge Transfer describes how knowledge and ideas move between knowledge sources to the potential users of the knowledge. It consists of a variety of activities which aim to capture and pass on knowledge, skills and competences from those who generate them to those who can use them (Ní Cheallacháin et al. n.d.). Knowledge transfer within an organisation is the process where one unit (e.g. group, department or division) is affected by the experience of another, which involves the transfer of knowledge at the individual level and transcends to transfer across higher organisational levels, and externally (Argote and Ingram, 2000). **Knowledge transfer through training** is important for delivering a transdisciplinary project like DIRECTED because the knowledge produced must be transferred as efficiently and effectively as possible to have the greatest impact.

Figure 2: Overview of the DIRECTED Real World Labs in Europe with their specific DRM/ CCA challenges.

Examples of knowledge transfer activities identified across the literature and in-practice that support capacity and learning are outlined in Table 1. For Training in DIRECTED, and for exploration in this deliverable, we prioritise and focus on professional training activities/mechanisms. However, we will support university teaching where opportunities arise and through other tasks and deliverables support knowledge transfer through communication, dissemination, policy and exploitation activities (as described in more detail in following sub-sections).

Table 1: Types of Knowledge Transfer activities or mechanisms.

Types of KT	Examples of activities or mechanisms	Interplay with other deliverables
Professional Training	Continual professional development (CPD) / online training module (certified) or in-person training/ workshops; Webinar or e-Learning series (self-taught or facilitated); On-the-job project work; Site visits/ tours; Mentoring; Conference/ workshop/ event organisation; Personnel movement/ secondment; intermediary or translator roles / boundary spanning; Joint grant/ funding acquisition	D6.4 – E-Learning Platform D4.1 – Knowledge co-production modules for Training-of-Trainers D5.7 – Data Fabric User Training per Role
University teaching	Dedicated postgraduate courses; Accredited modules (across disciplines) in third level/ universities; Micro-credentials; Resources, case studies, scientific literature / materials for embedding in existing modules; Summer schools; Mobility/ exchanges; Internships/ practical projects; Mentoring/ supervision	D6.4 – E-Learning Platform
Communication/ Dissemination	Online accessible resources in knowledge sharing platform/ portal; Social media dissemination of knowledge outputs; Exchange at relevant conferences, forums, meetings, workshops online and in-person; Knowledge networks/ partnerships/ forums	D6.1 – Communications Strategy
Policy/ Advocacy	Policy briefs / advocacy key messages / lessons learned; Policy dialogues/ conversations with policymakers	D3.3 – Policy brief on risk governance in the DRM and CCA D3.4 – Guidance on good practices regarding interoperability of governance D6.9 – Legacy document on capacity/ skills for risk and adaptation management
Exploitation	Technology transfer; intellectual property/ patents; spin-off/ enterprise creation	D6.5 – Business Development Plan

The scope of individuals and organisations that are engaged in, or could benefit from, knowledge transfer activities through DIRECTED are represented in different layers in Figure 3. This includes Real World Lab facilitators/ hosts (DIRECTED consortium members leading

engagements see blue inner circle). RWL core stakeholder groups (a mix of representation across practitioners, policymakers, academics/researchers and NGOs/ civil society, public/private sector, municipal authority representatives) and wider stakeholders and public in each RWL context that are not directly involved (see outer blue circles). DIRECTED consortium partners/ organisations representing RWL countries or regions and other country contexts in Europe i.e. UK, Switzerland and Ireland (see orange circle). Other European stakeholders including civil society, DRM/ CCA organisations and consortiums that can learn from the knowledge generated in DIRECTED (e.g. EU level policymakers) and exchange knowledge with DIRECTED (e.g. sister Horizon consortium projects). Knowledge transfer and exchange could target these groups and in-between them, as represented through the arrows in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Knowledge transfer potential within DIRECTED.

1.2 Key exploitable results for training

Horizon Europe defines a Key Exploitable Result (KER) as an identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits in the downstream value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

In DIRECTED, we identify KERs as the knowledge outputs developed through the projects deliverables that can generate additional value for users within and beyond the consortium (such as those listed in Figure 3). Within Work Package 6, two specific tasks and related deliverables outlined below are designed to implement the Knowledge Transfer Plan, by developing and maintaining training and education related activities.

- Development of training-of-trainers programme and curriculum development (Task 6.4) and identification of an e-Learning portal (D6.4).
- Pilot tracking of knowledge transfer and training implementation and application of integrated governance and technical tools (Task 6.5) and legacy document on the capacity/ skills for risk and adaptation management (D6.9).

Horizon Europe recommends prioritizing KERs based on the a) degree of innovation, b) exploitability and c) impact. Here we prioritize KERs based on the extent to which they can be used to support continued training and capacity development for end-users within and beyond the lifetime of the project and if they can have a specific impact on policy design and implementation. The Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric are identified as the two overarching KERs, which are explained further below along with their associated deliverables relevant for knowledge transfer.

Risk-Tandem Framework – enables the delivery of transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes, risk analysis, capacity strengthening, evaluation and learning in the DIRECTED Real World Labs. Details on the conceptual development of the Framework can be found in Deliverable 3.1 (Schweizer et al. 2024). It combines co-production and risk governance approaches to support RWLs to develop DRM and CCA solutions with stakeholders by connecting knowledge via co-production and co-exploration, identifying decision-relevant needs in an iterative process, increasing capacities, and strengthening communication and networks that can enable more disaster resilience across institutions, sectors and scales. Coping with uncertainty, strengthening resilience and supporting transformative learning are central components of Risk-Tandem. The following deliverables relate to Risk-Tandem as a KER:

- Framework process design (D3.1) application (D1.4) and iteration (D3.2) in the Real World Labs and recommendations for policy on risk governance (D3.3) and good practice for governance mechanisms and interoperability (D3.4).
- Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2) and modules for Training-of-Trainers workshops in designing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes (D4.1).
- Forensic examination/ case studies of DRM/ CCA processes and event management (D1.3).

Knowledge co-production is a central focus of the DIRECTED project especially within the Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric. Transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes through Tandem focuses on strengthening capacity of all participants and relevant institutions, and building trust to effectively co-produce relevant, usable information for decision-making (Daniels et al. 2020). In DIRECTED, co-production involves close working collaboration and exploration with identified RWL stakeholders including technical specialists (modellers, data scientists) and practitioners (emergency managers, disaster risk managers, planners) at all stages of project development and implementation. A Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2) and supporting capacity development modules are specifically designed to train and guide ‘trainers’ (in this case, RWL hosts) in this co-production process so that they can design similar processes with stakeholders in their own contexts. The complexity of risk

and related integrated DRM and CCA technical and governance solutions require interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary expertise, going beyond subject matter expertise, such as engineering or natural sciences, to capture tacit knowledges required for collaboration, information exchange, or the mobilization of resources (including relationships and trust) (Fisher and Jasny, 2017). The Risk-Tandem Framework consequently also provides a conceptual lens to adequately frame the respective RWLs in relation to their institutional context, highlighting and assessing the formal and informal decision-making structures that underlie DRM and CCA processes.

Data Fabric — an integrated yet federated system, that connects different instances of tools and data sources on premises, public and private clouds under a centralized platform that can adapt to changing CCA and DRM requirements. The Front-End provides access to the Fabric and its data and model catalogue to users via a unified web interface with data visualization and dashboards. It uses open source software such as GeoServer, pygeoapi and builds upon open standards defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC). Where open access is not permissible for RWL systems we provide a separate Back-End with restricted access. The DIRECTED Data Fabric integrates existing models and data sets that are developed by project partners for the use in our RWLs and beyond. External services including models and data hubs such as the Copernicus Climate Data Store will be made available via APIs to all users of the Data Fabric. The following deliverables relate to the Data Fabric as a KER:

- Data Fabric design (D5.1/5.2/5.3) and implementation including configured RWL Interoperability Use Cases (D5.4/5.5) with user training by role (D5.7).
- Interoperability demonstration factsheets (D2.3) and compendium on data standards (D2.1).

Integrated into the Data Fabric – are a set of tools developed and maintained by the consortium partners to be used in and beyond the RWL contexts. These tools are updated in a co-development process with the RWL stakeholders to better suit their needs and improving interoperability (D2.2) raising their TRL levels to bring innovations into use by DRM/ CCA practitioners (See Table 6). The Data Fabric provides the interfaces improving the tools interoperability and visualisation (D5.5). Each of these tools will come with improved documentation, manuals and training material to make them more accessible for:

- Further development by technical experts, modellers and software developers
- Integration by DRM/ CCA practitioners in their organisations workflows
- Visualisation and communication of risk between actors in DRM/ CCA including non-technical users such as volunteers

2 Methodology

2.1 Objective

The Gaps and Opportunities Assessment was conducted by collecting information from multiple sources to inform the Knowledge Transfer Plan. The objective of this assessment is to inform and support the knowledge transfer and training activities in Task 6.4 which involves the co-development of programmes to support **integrated responses to multi-hazard risk and CCA**. These training programmes will support wider application and scaling by other DRM/ CCA professionals of the KERs in DIRECTED – Data Fabric (including the integrated models) and the Risk-Tandem Framework being applied and tested in the Real World Labs. Specifically the gaps and opportunities assessment:

- Reviews **training and education opportunities** related to integrated multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation available in the European context. See Section 3.
- Identifies knowledge gaps and training needs for supporting integrated responses to DRM and CCA based on a desktop review and insights emerging from RWLs and consortium partners, including the availability/ use of such training (or others). See Section 4.
- Identifies different end-user groups for training and puts forward a Knowledge Transfer Plan (KTP) to address the gaps and needs identified including content, medium, channel and impact measurement that the KERs can address. See Section 5.
- Identifies a pathway towards impact and exploitation (or business development) beyond the training materials/ programmes developed. See Section 6.

Note this assessment aimed to take a wider perspective than our specific RWL contexts, because the specific training needs of the RWLs for knowledge co-production is addressed in the Capacity Development strategy (D1.2) and here we are aiming for wider scaling up of the learning and tools developed through our RWLs and supporting on the integration of technical and governance frameworks.

2.2 Approach

The following methods were used to develop the assessment: 1) scoping survey with consortium; 2) key informant interviews; 3) desktop review; and, 4) analysis of data emerging from RWLs.

A **scoping survey** with consortium partners (June 2023) to gain initial baseline insights into the existing institutional capacities, training and educational activities. The survey results helped to identify areas for improvement that DIRECTED can address to facilitate the transfer

of knowledge within their institutions and across their engaged stakeholder groups and networks. The list of survey questions is presented in Annex 1. We recognise that targeting only the consortium limited the responses from other DRM/ CCA professionals. However, it was deemed appropriate at the time because the relationships between RWL stakeholders and their hosts were still developing and pressure to complete additional surveys was not deemed appropriate. Furthermore, the insights shared from the DIRECTED Consortium does represent a wider circle of influence and knowledge beyond their organisations, as many of the partners have worked with agencies/ (non) governmental bodies, other high performing research institutes and international actors in the context of DRM and CCA.

To complement these initial findings additional data and feedback was collated by **analysing RWL workshop data** and conducting **bilateral discussions and exchange with RWL hosts** and stakeholders (where possible, e.g. during General Assemblies). These DRM and CCA practitioners have experience working with an extensive network of relevant actors within and beyond their geographical remit spanning professional, practice and policy domains.

Key informant discussions with other EU projects and institutional contacts working in the DRM/ CCA space were completed to support in identifying existing training opportunities and help clarify the gaps, identify entry points for knowledge transfer and opportunities for collaboration. The key informant discussions involved meetings online and in-person at relevant events such as EU project meetings exchanges (e.g. The Hut; PEERS; C2IMPRESS; PARATUS; MEDiate; Myriad; REACH-OUT; and UNIC), e-Learning entry points (e.g. EU Citizen Science portal, weADAPT and Climate Ireland), and broader conversations at conferences and events (e.g. European Climate Change Adaptation Conference (ECCA, June, Dublin 2023), European Geosciences Union General Assembly (Vienna, April 2023), and the Project to Policy Seminar (Brussels, June 2023)).

Desktop review of scientific and grey literature on knowledge transfer, as well as web searches for relevant e-Learning and knowledge sharing platforms, synergies with EU projects and training programmes and EU-level policy and learning frameworks was performed. This involved reviewing existing training and educational programmes (European and sometimes global) covering e-Learning, online guidelines/toolkits, communities of practice, tailored training and educational/ professional development programmes. Additionally, scoping opportunities for collaboration with other EU projects and identifying additional entry points within partners institutions.

3 Existing training and learning opportunities in DRM & CCA

Reviewing existing training and education opportunities related to multi-risk management and climate adaptation reveals different ways that practitioners, policymakers and scientists can access knowledge and learn about risk management and climate adaptation. These opportunities are grouped as follows and explained in the following sub-sections:

- e-Learning courses or modules developed by different organisations and hosted by different learning management systems or websites.
- Online (interactive) guides aimed at supporting practitioners and policymakers to strengthen governance or technical staff/ scientists who want to integrate software.
- Communities of practice and networks, signposting to trainings / events and other learning resources and opportunities such as recorded webinars, conferences/ events, summer schools.
- Tailored or targeted training support.
- Education (third level) or training courses (CPD).

Within each sub-section we discuss the relevance and accessibility of each learning/ training opportunity for different end-users, and reflect on experiences of the DIRECTED RWL hosts and consortium members in accessing or delivering training or guidance. We also identify the opportunities that relate more strongly to enhancing knowledge around data, modelling and tools integration and those aimed at enhancing governance and communication capacity among DRM/ CCA professionals or interested citizens/ volunteers.

The importance of identifying a variety of learning and training opportunities was clear from the survey, especially the results from RWL hosts (i.e. DRM/ CCA practitioners). Facilitated learning online e.g., through webinars and online e-Learning ranked the highest among Real World Lab hosts (see Figure 3), followed by independent learning (e.g., open access videos, PDFs/ PowerPoint materials). In-person teaching and learning e.g., through summer schools, workshops, informing university modules and guest lecturing was the lowest ranking. This demonstrates the importance of going beyond making learning resources openly accessible online, but connecting the materials to both online and in-person teaching and learning activities.

In Section 4 we discuss the specific knowledge gaps emerging from insights on the needs identified in RWLs, in combination with the desktop review, survey and key-informant discussions and reflect on how this can inform training needs for DIRECTED to address through the Knowledge Transfer Plan (Section 5).

Figure 4: Real World Lab host preferences for learning approaches.

3.1 e-Learning courses or modules

At the National, European and global level, online e-Learning training opportunities exist for professionals and volunteers (or interested citizens) to upskill around specific areas related to CCA, DRM and risk management — as listed in Table 2. Limited courses were found that focus on the integration or interoperability of technical and governance frameworks. E-Learning trainings covering specific topics within DRM and CCA were identified e.g. citizen engagement, nature based solutions, data management and risk modelling. Additional trainings were identified emerging from the humanitarian sector but were not included unless also relevant for the European disaster and climate communities. Many training programs provide general knowledge applicable to broad audiences but lack tailored content that addresses specific local climate and disaster risks including urban/ rural contexts. Courses that target DRM and CCA professionals were prioritised, however, those courses targeting citizens, volunteers and technical professionals (modellers, scientists) and were included to capture the range of training resources available.

The approach to e-Learning varied across the different trainings, but a majority of the courses were hosted by a Learning Management System (LMS) such as Moodle or OpenEdx which requires the user to register and sign up, specify expected hours of learning and offer certification upon completion. Other courses are hosted by LMS and learning materials are openly accessible without registering but are not certified (e.g. the Including Citizens Handbook courses from the LINKS project). Some e-Learning courses specifically targeted public sector staff for training and were not open to the public (e.g. Local Authority Climate Action Training Programme in Ireland).

Reflecting on these e-Learning courses, it is clear that many training resources exist for DRM/ CCA professionals who would benefit from them but are likely not aware of them. Based on

discussions with RWLs, there is limited awareness or use of these courses within their organisations. As such, this highlights the importance of disseminating such courses via relevant communities and networks (discussed further in sub-section 3.3).

Courses and modules developed in research projects often become unavailable with the completion of the project and the end of funding for hosting of the e-Learning resources. This disappearance of e-Learning resources is especially apparent when they are hosted on project websites. Two viable avenues for publicising e-Learning modules are currently prevalent:

1. Renting server space on with commercial LMS platform providers such as Udemy, Coursera or LinkedIn Learning.
2. Self-hosting of an LMS on long term funded servers using systems like Moodle, OpenEdx or LearnPress.

Commercial LMS providers mostly offer well polished and maintained websites and apps for users to interact with the e-Learning content. The service has to be paid for by the content provider and usually also requires users to create accounts to access the platform. Commercial platforms may also use uploaded training content for advertising purposes.

Self-hosted LMS require more technical expertise on the part of the training provider, but allow for more granular control over how e-Learning material is presented. The server hosting the LMS has to be funded long term to ensure that the resources are findable and accessible beyond a project's lifetime. These systems can rely on open source software and can be set up to make training modules accessible without the barrier of login or account creation. Annex 3 provides an overview of available e-Learning systems and LMS providers.

Table 2: E-Learning modules/ courses available related to risk management and climate adaptation.

Training opportunity	Host/ Funder	Focus/ objective	Target group	Learning approach
<u>Thought Leadership Course - Synergizing Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation</u>	United Nations System Staff College / UNDRM	Focus on understanding synergies between DRM and CCA	Decision-makers and DRM and CCA focal points involved in developing DRM strategies and adaptation plans across levels.	E-Learning, self-paced, 2-hours, English, no certification
<u>Cities and Climate Change</u>	UN-Habitat and UN CC:Learn	Integrating Climate Change Adaptation into urban planning	Civil servants, managers in private sector/ civil society organisations working on climate change and/or urban development, researchers/ students and interested citizens.	E-Learning course, 2 hours, with certification
<u>Civil Protection Mechanism Training Programme</u>	Civil Protection Knowledge Network	Increase the UCPM response capability and better prepare for disasters, and supplements the national training offer provided to experts by their countries and organisations.	Civil protection and disaster management experts from EU Member States and Union Civil Protection Mechanism Participating States	E-Learning Varying durations
<u>Making Cities Resilient: Developing Local Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience Strategies</u>	UNITAR / UNDRM	Integration of DRM and CCA into urban planning. Using Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities to assess risk management and developing safe and resilient country/ city plan.	City and local government officials, disaster management professionals, and representatives from academic and training institutions working on Disaster Risk Reduction and sustainable development.	E-Learning, 6 modules fixed time period, self-paced, certified, English
<u>Making Climate Adaptation Happen: Governing Transformation</u>	University of Groningen and Global Centre on Adaptation	Climate science and controversies Climate adaptation governance	Policymakers (intermediate level)	E-Learning 4 weeks / 4hrs per week (limited/ restricted access), English

<u>Strategies for Climate Change</u>		Climate finance Nature-based solutions		Future Learn platform
<u>Transitioning to complex risk management and resilient urban futures: harnessing south-south cooperation and learning from COVID-19</u>	UN Office for South-South Cooperation (UNOSSC), UNDRM Global Education and Training Institute (UNDRM GETI), the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Pan American Health Organization (PAHO).	Increase the understanding and capacities to manage complex and systematic disaster risks	Local and national government officials in charge of Disaster Risk Reduction and management, urban development and planning, public health; emergency preparedness, national associations of municipalities; urban resilience and development practitioners, as well as civil society, private sector, and academia.	E-Learning, 4 hours, certified, self-paced, English
<u>Raising Awareness – Local Authority Climate Action Training Programme</u>	Local Authority Climate Action Training Programme. UCC, CARO, Climate Ireland, EPA and Met Eireann	Support in increasing awareness of climate change, and the role, of the local authorities and opportunities for climate action	Local authority staff in Ireland only	E-Learning, 1.5 hours, English (closed to staff)
<u>European Citizen Science training</u>	EU Citizen Science Funded by European Union	Courses on various citizen science topics	General audience / those working with citizen science initiatives	E-Learning, various duration, some certified.
<u>Nature-based Solutions for Disaster and Climate Resilience</u>	SDG AcademyX UNEP	Introduction to nature-based solutions for disaster and climate resilience, benefits and opportunities and modules focused on practical applications by target audiences.	All backgrounds and levels (youth leader, practitioner, policy maker, engineer, or business owner).	E-Learning, 7 weeks, 3-6 hours per week, self-paced, certified, English.
<u>Disaster, Crisis and Emergency Preparedness Communication</u>	The State University of New York via Coursera	Modules on emergency management, planning,	General audience	E-Learning, 9 hours, online, self-paced, English (other

		vulnerability and crisis risk communication.		languages available via translation)
<u>LINKS Citizens Handbook and e-Learning courses</u>	LINKS Horizon 2020 project Community Centre	Four courses 1) Communicating Risk 2) Making Information Accessible 3) Mobilising Citizens 4) Mobilising Volunteers each with multiple modules and a supporting handbook. Explainer videos, examples and recommendations included.	Disaster Management Organisations, first responders and decision makers. Also, businesses and academic researchers.	E-Learning, self-paced online, not certified, no time duration, languages (English, German, Danish, Dutch and Italian) LMS – Rise Articulate
<u>Participate!</u>	International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) and Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre within the framework of the Zurich Flood Resilience Alliance	Interactive online training module to support the design of effective science, policy and practice events. Focuses on participatory meetings such as workshops, conferences and training courses	Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) communities.	E-Learning (account required)
<u>SCORE MOOC</u>	Score project EU Horizon 2020	Course 1: What are Nature Based Solutions? (focus on how NBS can help address environmental challenges). Course 2: Ecosystem-based approaches (focus on implementation using living labs, co-creation, technology use and citizen science) (other courses planned)	Students, citizens, climate enthusiasts	E-Learning, 1-4 hours content, sign-in required, English

Civil Protection Volunteers Training <u>CiProVot e-Learning Platform</u>	ciprovot-project	CiProVoT aims to develop a Trans-national training course module for Civil Protection Volunteers (partly peer-education/partly with the use of external expert trainers).	Civil Protection/emergency management volunteers	E-Learning, English, Italian, Portuguese, Greek, (requires a free account) moodle system
EVANDE - Enhancing Volunteer Awareness and education against Natural Disasters through e-Learning	EVANDE project	The e-Learning platform aims to offer training opportunities to civil protection volunteers and local authorities' staff in Greece, Italy, Spain and Bulgaria. It supports interactive services between the instructors and the trainees and operates 4 web-seminars (educational programs) on earthquakes, floods, forest fires and European civil protection policies.	Civil Protection volunteers	E-Learning, English, Italian, Spanish, Greek, Bulgarian (requires a free account) (offers certification) Coursevo system
E-Learning for the Prevention, Preparedness and Response to Natural Disasters	Frederiksborg Fire & Rescue Service and partners co-funded by EU Erasmus+ programme	Prevention, preparedness and response to four types of natural disasters: floods, storms, heat waves and wildfires.	4 different modules each targeting 1) primary school children, 2) secondary school students, 3) adults and 4) fire and rescue services professionals	E-Learning, Danish, English, Estonian, Lithuanian, Romanian and Spanish
Integrating Climate Risk Information into National Adaptation Plans NAPs	UN CC: e-Learn WMO, UNITAR, GFCS	Shows how to strengthen NAPs through appropriate climate information and coordinated policy action, drawing on the resources of the global hydro-	Climate services providers (National Hydro-meteorological Services, research/academic and international organizations), and users (e.g. decision	E-Learning, 6 hours, self-paced, certified, English.

		meteorological community.	makers, private investors, non-governmental organizations, etc.), as well as of those working at the science-policy interface for outreach or communication purposes.	
<u>National Adaptation Plans Building Climate Resilience in Agriculture MOOC/ Toolkit</u>	UNDP, FAO and UNITAR	Modules covering CCA, agriculture and food security, international frameworks and NAPs, assessing climate impacts and risks, adaptation options, governance and finance and communications, monitoring and evaluation.	Global practitioners/policymakers interested in Climate Change Adaptation	E-Learning, Learning materials hosted on FAO website (originally part of MOOC on UN CC: Learn platform) Self-based
<u>REACH OUT Shaping Climate Resilience Cities Learning Program</u>	REACHOUT Project (Learning program led by Resilient Cities Network) EU Horizon 2020	Module 1: Resilience Fundamentals, Climate Risk Assessment and Story-Mapping Module 2: Fundamentals of Climate Services, and Stakeholder Engagement Module 3: Pathways for Resilience and Monitoring and Evaluation climate adaptation	City Hub representatives in REACHOUT	Facilitated via webinars and materials available online in PDF deliverables, English. No LMS.
<u>Risk-informed Governance and Innovative Technology for Disaster Risk Reduction and Resilience</u>	UNDESA, DPIDG, UNPOG, and UNDRM	Build capacities to spearhead innovations and utilize ICT and key frontier technologies in the government in order to drive Disaster Risk	Government practitioners/policymakers	E-Learning, self-paced, 5 hours, certified, English

		Reduction and resilience		
<u>Academy Module on ICT for Disaster Risk Management</u>	UN ESCAP	introduces Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and provides an overview of how information and communication technologies (ICTs) can be used for DRM.	General audience	E-Learning, self-paced, varying duration, English.
<u>Academy module on ICT for Climate Resilient Development</u>	UNESCAP	how ICTs can be used to enhance climate resilient development including how to Strengthen integration and partnerships	General audience	E-Learning, self-paced, varying duration, English.
<u>Introduction to Impact-based forecast warning services (IBFWS)</u>	World Meteorological Organisation Education and Training Programme	Advance an impact-based approach in hydro-meteorological services, Disaster Risk Reduction and related areas.	General audience	E-Learning, self-paced, 2 hours, English, certified Moodle WMO
<u>Copernicus MOOC</u>	Copernicus (European Union Space programme)	Understanding Copernicus data and services, learning from success stories	First-time and intermediate users interested to harness space data for innovation	E-Learning, self-paced, English.
<u>ECMWF e-Learning modules for example 1) using climate models for climate scenarios and 2) Climate projections and 3) Uncertainty, Robustness and Confidence</u>	ECMWF	Learn about climate data types, who uses them, and how they contribute to societal benefit	General audience (anyone interested in learning about climate data)	E-Learning, self-paced, varying duration, English.
<u>Open Geospatial Consortium standards e-Learning tutorial</u>	Open Geospatial Consortium	Familiarisation with OGC standards	General audience interested in OGC standards	E-Learning, self-paced, free

<u>Introduction to Climate Risk Informed Decision Analysis (CRIDA)</u>	UNESCO Open Learning	12 modules introducing the Climate Risk Informed Decision Analysis (CRIDA), a collaborative approach to address an uncertain future.	General audience	E-Learning, Fixed time period, self-paced, 12 hours
MOOC on role of models in risk assessment and how to use the Oasis Loss Modelling Framework	OASIS LMF, CLIMATE-KIC AND NERC	Introduction to catastrophe modelling and the Oasis Loss Modelling Framework, and Oasis tools.	Insurance sector, scientists/ modellers	E-Learning, self-paced, content organised over 4 weeks (hours required not specified), English, no login/ account required

3.2 Online guides for governance and technical support

Two groups or areas of (interactive) online guidance were identified as part of the review, as presented in Table 3. Firstly, guidance in the form of interactive frameworks or toolkits aiming to build governance and institutional capacity for climate adaptation planning. These were found to primarily target coordinators, managers or facilitators to advance processes and actions for climate adaptation. For example, the Adaptation Support Tool (European Environment Agency) provides guidance for those responsible to develop climate adaptation strategies (from national to municipal level) and supports in risk and impact assessment, and the selection of measures and evaluation. Others target facilitators who can support interactive and/ or knowledge processes to support in co-developing climate services (e.g. Tandem Framework) or climate risk management and related dialogue (e.g. Climate Training Kit for Red Cross Red Crescent Movement). Such guides provide links to case studies/ examples and further resources to support learners' needs. These guides provide a more interactive experience for the user, with clickable graphics and drop-down menus, allowing users to identify content of specific interest, in comparison to basic PDF toolkits (many of which exist).

Secondly, guidance specifically for implementing scientific hazard and risk modelling tools and associated frameworks were identified. These are aimed towards software developers, data/ modelling scientists in public agencies (e.g. National Meteorological agencies in the case of CLIMADA or GIS/technical staff in Danish municipalities in the case of the Cost Damage

Assessment Tool) and often PhD students or researchers who are applying or further developing the models. The guidance most commonly comes in the form of 'README's' hosted on version control platforms such as GitHub/Gitlab and in some cases are very detailed and provide guiding video tutorials, access to real or test datasets (e.g. CLIMADA) for the learner to implement or integrate the model directly. The level of detail and quality of guidance varies greatly and in most cases assumes an understanding of technical setups and software development environments. Providing guidance and transfer transferring knowledge via README files is considered best practice in the software development community. Most DRM/CCA actors without the technical (IT) background will have difficulties finding these repositories of knowledge and recognising the learning opportunities they offer.

As all of the guidance is open-access and doesn't require log-in so the hosts/ organisations producing the content cannot identify who has used the guidance. However, access to some modelling tools (e.g. RIM2D) are not fully open yet but is planned within the DIRECTED project. Interestingly both the governance related guidance (e.g. Climate Adaptation Partnership Framework) and technical guidance are hosted on GitHub. This is recognised as an online space for hosting learning materials that is not dependent on project websites (with defined timelines) or LMS with hosting fees. RWLs and scientific/ research partners are committed to ensuring that materials and outputs generated through DIRECTED are available openly and easily accessible to others. This will be prioritised in the selection of the e-Learning platform for sustaining access to knowledge resources beyond the project website.

The review identifies a lack of guidelines available for an 'intermediate user' who has some technical background but requires an easier user experience and visualisation of the model outputs and help to guide practical applications in operations or planning. For example, ETH Zurich, through project U-CLIMADAPT, CLIMADA is developing a dashboard like interface to train and guide forecasters (German, Swiss, Austrian and French) on impact-based forecasting. Users/ learners can visualise results through maps and plots with pre-computed extreme forecast events and Users can integrate Copernicus data, and complete post-processing e.g. overlap with heat index. Users can then experiment with different variables (via interactive Jupyter Notebooks) and visualise results without needing to code. Developing such interactive training materials (for online learning) requires significant effort, but the possibilities can be explored through the Data Fabric. An upcoming service in the [European Open Science Cloud – EU Node](#) may be used to host interactive guides like Jupyter Notebooks and full test setups for exploration.

Table 3: List of online interactive tools available targeting practitioners working on DRM/ CCA.

Training opportunity	Host	Focus/ objective	Target group	Learning approach
<u>Climate Adaptation Support Tool</u>	Climate-Adapt / European Environment Agency	Practical guidance tool outlining the steps needed to develop, implement, monitor and evaluate adaptation strategies.	Policymakers and coordinators of adaptation plans and strategies	Online guideline , self-paced.
<u>Climate Training Kit</u>	Red Cross Red Crescent Climate Centre	Innovative and interactive training tools related to climate	Trainers and facilitators in the Red Cross Red Crescent Movement	Online guideline, self-paced.
<u>TANDEM online guidance</u>	SEI Initiative on Climate Services	A guiding framework to collaboratively co-design and co-develop adaptation solutions and climate services using transdisciplinary processes to promote long-term climate resilience.	Climate information providers, intermediaries, knowledge brokers, planners, advisors, decision makers, researchers and practitioners	Interactive online guideline with embedded resources
<u>Scotland Adapts Capability Framework</u>	Adaptation Scotland	A capability framework with embedded resources for a Climate Ready Public Sector identifying tasks to develop capabilities over 4 stages.	Public sector employees in Scotland supporting climate adaptation	Interactive online guideline with embedded resources
<u>Climate Adaptation Partnership Framework</u>	Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange TALX project (Irish Environment Protection Agency funded)	Outlines actions for adaptation action under four capability areas – Leadership, Evidence, Partnership and Resources.	Open to anyone who aims to build/ support climate adaptation partnerships	Interactive online guideline hosted on GitHub with embedded resources
<u>CLIMADA Economics of Climate Adaptation (online guidance)</u>	ETH Zurich, Weather and Climate Risks Research Group	Tutorials and guidance on how to implement CLIMADA - fully probabilistic risk assessment model. Including <u>README</u> to understand how to run the model	Technical specialists (modellers) in academia or practice	Guideline, self-paced

<u>CLIMADA open library</u>	ETH Zurich, Weather and Climate Risks Research Group	Scientific publications on the methodology behind CLIMADA and case studies using CLIMADA	Technical specialists (modellers) in academia or practice	Literature self-study Zotero
<u>GeoServer guidance</u>	GeoServer team	GeoServer documentation with user and developer manuals	Technical specialists (developers and users) in academia or practice	Self-study
<u>Danube Model</u>	OASIS HUB, PIK, University of Tokyo	<u>Technical documentation</u> of the model components <u>Hydrological model (SWIM)</u> <u>Hydrodynamic model (CaMa-Flood)</u>	Advanced users and modelling experts	Publicly available report and metadata for self-study
<u>Cost Damage Assessment Model Guidance</u>	Danish Technical University	Model development and setup	Technical documentation for developers and advanced users	Publicly available README on Github (self-guided)
<u>RIM 2D</u>	GFZ Potsdam	Model development and setup	Technical documentation for developers and advanced users	Available to invited users on Gitlab in README format (self-guided)

3.3. Communities of practice

The review identified that a range of training and support is available through a number of Communities of Practice, networks or forums that bring together different groups of practitioners, policymakers and scientists around DRM and CCA and disseminate or host learning opportunities. Table 3 presents these communities including knowledge platforms like PreventionWeb targeting the DRM community more broadly on range of topics, the European Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre with a stronger focus on DRM data and risk analysis, and weADAPT broadly targeting the CCA community. Such knowledge platforms have specific areas (or corners) where training opportunities including e-Learning courses, (recorded) webinars, conferences, and events, as well as third-level university courses, and paid professional development are available (past and upcoming) and disseminated. Another community is the Societal Resilience Cluster (SRC) facilitated by the CMINE project. The Cluster is an informal and voluntary community for European Research and Innovation for Security (CERIS) projects working on thematic and related research areas under the Disaster Resilient Societies (DRS) framework. This community offers opportunities to connect with other DRM/ CCA practitioners working towards similar goals and support cross-pollination of ideas and opportunities for knowledge transfer and learning.

Although platforms like PreventionWeb or weADAPT, do enable sharing of DRM and CCA knowledge between major stakeholders (Weichselgartner and Pigeon, 2015; Spiekermann, et al., 2015), the RWLs within the DIRECTED consortium were not found to be using these global platforms to access learning resources and training. Instead access to training is primarily gained through national networks or forums, some examples listed in Table 3, or those advertised through their organisations. Additionally, RWL hosts were found to access training through internal working groups (in the case of Erftverband, Germany) and national authority led training for the case of Zala, Hungary. All of the RWL hosts indicated that their organisations provided opportunities to access training and skills development around DRM/ CCA through attendance at events, webinars and conferences. Such conferences include the European Geosciences Union which includes short courses and presentations on topics including natural hazards and hydrology, or the RISK-KAN community and its working group focusing on multi-hazard and compounding risk. However, such conferences typically target scientists and research communities and are less attended by practitioners given the cost and time commitment for participation. In some cases, the learning material is open to the public e.g. Society for Risk Analysis posts webinars online, and in other cases are closed e.g. EGU.

From the technical modelling and tool development perspective, the importance of access to communities for users to ask questions and provide feedback and guidance was identified. This can be in the form of email, chat forums or organised meetings/ forums. For example, CLIMADA runs a monthly meeting open to users, and answers questions on GitHub and Slack overflow. Other technical tools organise events to bring together users (from science and practice) to share experiences, for example Delft-FEWS User Days organised by Deltares. Communities like the MI4Adapt offers opportunities for CCA professionals (e.g. city planners, climate adaptation coordinators, mayors) to connect and exchange experiences through

online events such as the Peer Learning Programme for Charter Signatories. Overall, we recognise that it is not enough to just offer a training course on a specific governance or technical framework/ tool, and there is a need support ongoing exchange and mentoring to support users through existing communities, networks or forums.

Furthermore, these communities of practice or forums play an important role in disseminating the e-Learning and training to a wider audience. As such, a layered approach is needed to ensure dissemination across multiple channels including national platforms and organisational networks (often in local languages) to reach more DRM/ CCA professionals.

Table 4: Identified communities of practice, forums or networks supporting knowledge exchange, training and learning around multi-risk management and climate adaptation.

Training opportunity	Host	Focus/ objective	Target group	Learning approach
<u>Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre Training Corner</u>	European Commission/ Joint Research Centre	Online training series and learning materials on Science for DRM reports and other opportunities (workshops, trainings, webinars) on methodological and conceptual approaches and guidelines for disaster risk assessment and management.	Global/ European DRM professionals, scientists/ academics	Community-based, recorded webinars/workshops, online and in-person, various durations, English. Needs registration
Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt)/ Community of Practice	European Commission / Climate Adaptation	Community of Practice sharing training courses and relevant learning events. For example MIP4ADAPT Peer Learning Programme for Charter Signatories.	European regional and local authorities and some specifically for Charter signatories	Community-based (promoting online and in-person events) Needs registration
<u>PreventionWeb Training</u>	UNDRM	Capacity development on DRM themes and issues through training, online courses and webinars.	Global practitioners, policymakers, scientists and citizens	Community-based (promoting online and in-person events) Needs registration
<u>weADAPT Climate Adaptation Training theme</u>	SEI	Provides an organised collection of material and links to different training courses, workshops and other guidance.	Global practitioners, policymakers, scientists and citizens	Community-based (promoting online and in-person events) Free and open access. External

				courses may require registration.
<u>CERIS – Community for European Research and Innovation for Security /</u>	European Commission Home Affairs	Crisis Management Innovation Network Europe CMINE DRS01 Societal Resilience Cluster	European level Horizon project partners	Community-based (online and in-person events) <u>HOME-CERIS@ec.europa.eu</u> needs to be contacted to participate
<u>International Forum to Advance First Responder Innovation</u>	IFRAFI	Assess common global capability gaps Product solutions and research projects to the topic can be submitted Find projects that have worked with problems of first responders in the past	Academia and industry in regard for first responders needs	Provides analysis of problems, summaries and posters to inform Open access
<u>RISK-KAN Knowledge Action Network on Emergent Risks and Extreme Events</u>	Future Earth	Promotes the exchange of information, knowledge, and data	Scientists, experts, and communities focusing on multi-hazard risks, Disaster Risk Reduction, and governance of extreme events	Comprehensive inter- and transdisciplinary hub Host webinars Promotes in-person conferences/ events Some contents are open access, some need registration
<u>EGU Hydrological Sciences section and Natural Hazards section</u>		Short courses, splinter meetings,	Hydrologists, Forecasters, data scientists/ modellers, Natural Hazards scientists practitioners and policymakers	Not openly accessible
<u>Society for Risk Analysis</u>	Society for Risk Analysis	Working groups/ webinars forum for scientific discussion	Scientists, researchers	Open access
<u>Open Geospatial Consortium</u>	OGC	Helps finding geospatial information	Government, industry, and academia connected to geospatial	Open access for some online meetings and the search engine or

				become a member to take part in more
The national network for CCA Denmark (DNNK)	DNNK	Foster co-working and interoperability as a professional community in CCA	Municipalities, utilities, companies/ advisors and knowledge institutions working in CCA	In-person meetings, become a member to take part Danish
German Association for Water, Wastewater and Waste DWA-Fachgemeinschaft hydrologische Wissenschaften	German Association for Water, Wastewater and Waste	Certified Courses, seminars and qualifications for a lot of topics regarding water-management and hydrology	Researchers or employees in any field of hydrology	Online and in person for a fee German
<u>HydroForum</u>	<u>DHG Deutsche Hydrologische Gesellschaft</u>	Education and training in hydrology and water management in Germany, Austria and Switzerland	Mainly students in hydrology, geology, environmental sciences or similar	Summer schools, e-Learning (links to other websites)

Collaboration between European research projects offers opportunities to widen the network of DRM/ CCA practitioners that could inform and access the training developed within DIRECTED – through connections with a wider research and development ecosystem for DRM and CCA. By fostering collaboration, projects can share valuable insights and methodologies, ensuring that lessons learned from one initiative can be leveraged to benefit others. This collective approach also facilitates the knowledge transfer between Real World Labs, where researchers and stakeholders collaborate in real-world settings to co-create and test models, governance strategies and adaptation measures to strengthen societal resilience. There already exist many connections between European and national research projects in the DIRECTED consortium (Figure 5). Many DIRECTED partners are actively involved in other projects; this will enable us to overcome project-silos and improve knowledge transfer and training between projects and continuously strengthen communities of practice and networking beyond the lifetime of the projects.

Figure 5: Network of DIRECTED consortium members and partner projects.

3.4 Tailored and targeted support on-demand

The review identified that many organisations offer and access more tailored or targeted training based on the specific demands and needs. By design the online e-Learning courses lack follow-up support as they have a limited time duration and participants can find it difficult to apply what they have learned. An example of such tailored training emerged from Denmark, where the Danish the Association for Municipalities organised training with the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) specifically focused on their implementation and use of the Damage Cost Assessment Tool. The training involved installing the model on the municipalities system and supporting them to run it using their own data. This was a once-off training and not mandatory for all municipalities. The DTU team managing the model also offer a bilateral training session (1 hour) to those who sign up to the open source part of the model and are guided to use the README manual (as described in the previous sub-section). Additionally, the tool is being used in other EU projects with municipalities with similar bilateral support being provided by DTU. In the Rhine Ertf Region the University of Kaiserslautern-Landau, RPTU provides trainings for first responders, municipalities and other professional groups for coping with major flood and heavy rainfall events in German language with certification ([Weiterbildung-Fachbereich Bauingenieurwesen an der RPTU](#)). In the Zala Region, Hungary, The [Green City Hungary initiative](#) are a local network that provide practical trainings on city-level solutions around climate challenges.

Similarly, training with other technical tools is offered on a case-by-case basis if requested by a specific organisation. This one-on-one support is required when really trying to embed a specific technical tool/ model into an organisation. Typically, such tailored support comes at a cost to the organisation receiving it, and will vary depending on if the training is coming from a consultancy company (e.g. for SafterPlaces tool) or a university (e.g. for CLIMADA, RIM2D or DTU Cost Damage Assessment Tool).

In some cases, outreach about the capabilities of such modelling tools is requested by decision-makers or policymakers to present/ engage at specific events. For example, the European Central Bank requesting a more simplified presentation on CLIMADA to understand the benefits and potential to support their work.

The survey highlighted that RWLs access skills development via on-the-job training through involvement in different projects or training exercises. For example in Germany, the district of Euskirchen and Rhine-Erft both conduct disaster control exercises from time to time which offer a learning opportunity but these exercises are not necessarily focused on natural hazards, see more at Katastrophenschutzübung in Euskirchen - Kreisverwaltung Euskirchen (kreis-euskirchen.de) [Kommunenübergreifende Übungen | Rhein-Erft-Kreis](#). Other RWLs – Capital Region of Denmark and Emilia-Romagna also indicated the importance of simulations for strengthening communication and governance across stakeholders involved in their RWLs. In June 2024, a [Flood Exercise](#) with flood and storm surge simulations was organized as part the RWL activities to test communication and organizational procedures between volunteers, civil protection and municipalities, regional authorities and others. Such simulations provide insight into training and upskilling needs within the DRM/ CCA domain.

RWLs also highlighted the need for specialised workshops (online or in-person) and supporting guidelines that can focus on transferring knowledge around specific aspects of the project which link to existing deliverables, including Interoperability of tools (Data Fabric) (D5.7) and co-production multi-stakeholder workshop facilitation training (D4.1). As such, this tailored approach is important for the development of training on the Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric specifically in the RWLs because it will aim to really be embedded into organisations and future staff. As such, this should be organised within the duration of the projects and can be supported by additional interactive online guidance and e-Learning courses.

3.5 Education/ CPD programmes

As part of the review a number of educational or Continual Professional Development courses (typically coming with an associated cost) were identified from universities, professional training bodies and consultancies, as well as others offered directly through DRM or CCA related organisations.

Interdisciplinary programmes at postgraduate level DRM and CCA Masters Programme at Lund University, Sweden (which has been completed by some staff members in the Region Hovedstaden, Denmark, demonstrating its influence on future practitioners working on climate adaptation. University College London (a partner on sister project the Hut) offers master programmes on Risk and Disaster Reduction, Disaster Science and Resilience. Ingrassia et al. (2014) provides a review of educational programmes in disaster management, highlighting that despite national and international programmes, there is no standardised curriculum available to guide EU Member States. The [EUMA project](#) is focused on 'Creating a European Higher Education Network for Masters Programmes in Disaster Risk Management' with funding from Erasmus+, specifically targeting upskilling existing professionals working in civil protection agencies and disaster managers in the private sector. The network will foster collaboration with The Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network through for example summer schools and workshops. Micro-credentials offer an accessible way for bite-sized knowledge to be transferred between academia and industry/ practice, typically in the form of short courses offered via universities.

Overall, these postgraduate courses are not the focus of the review as through the project we aim to develop fully open access training materials available without the need to sign up to an accredited degree programme. However, such existing (or upcoming) courses, especially in the case of the EUMA project, offer an opportunity to integrate and embed the DIRECTED e-Learning materials into programmes that are reaching current or future DRM/ CCA practitioners. Furthermore, within the consortium there are entry points via universities to influence existing teaching materials through guest lecturing. Additionally, DIRECTED can support early career researchers through PhD or MSc. projects and summer schools to use and further develop the integrated technical and governance tools for multi-risk management and climate adaptation after the project ends. DIRECTED is co-organising the Multi-hazard Disaster Risk Reduction (DRM) Academy together with [PARATUS](#), [MYRIAD-EU](#), and [The HuT](#), bringing together 40 early career researchers and practitioners in Barcelona (October 23-26, 2024). Furthermore, the [Young Summer Scientist Program \(YSSP\)](#) organized by IASA hosts doctoral students to collaborate on their research and IASA has a newly established [capacity development summer school](#) focusing on systems modelling, as well as other summer training programs providing entry points for DIRECTED to engage with early career researchers.

In terms of professional development courses, insights were collected from the RWL host organisations around the types of trainings available to them or their RWL stakeholders. In the Zala Region Hungary, the Zalaegerszeg Vocational Training Center (Zalaegerszegi

Szakképzési Centrum - ZSZC) has multiple campuses in Zalaegerszeg, Keszthely, and Lenti. The institution offers courses related to climate change, such as environmental technician and green economy knowledge. These courses are primarily available to the working-age population and can be completed alongside work commitments. In the Emilia-Romagna Region, there is a course on the [management of climatic extreme events](#) including the operation of tools and technological skills targeting DRM professional are taught by partners at ARPAE. Another course organized by FAV with EU and RER funding include technical skills such as [IT and network security and development](#). The courses target professionals and are taught in Italian language.

4 Knowledge Gaps and Training Needs

As introduced in Section 1, DIRECTED aims to support interoperability and integration between different phases of DRM, as well as the between the various institutions and actors involved and between the data, methods and tools deployed to support DRM and CCA planning and practice. Doing so presents a pattern of complications resulting from knowledge gaps (or barriers) emerging from science, policy and practice, hindering actors' managing climate and disaster risks. This review focussed on identifying the knowledge gaps connected with a lack of interoperability or integration across the governance structures and communication processes, and the data, models and tools which support the many different tasks and decisions in DRM and CCA.

Figure 6 presents the six key gaps identified through engagement with Real World Labs (hosts), and emerging from grey and scientific literature. The project aims to bridge these gaps through work package tasks and activities, however, here we focus more specifically on what these knowledge gaps mean for training and knowledge transfer needs. Each of the six key gaps will be discussed in more detail including their associated Knowledge Gaps and Training Needs - synthesising information from the different methodological steps to provide an informed picture of gaps.

Figure 6: Main knowledge gaps interoperability in DRM and CCA addressed by DIRECTED.

4.1 Transdisciplinary collaboration

Knowledge Gap:

Interaction between the individual components of the DRM and CCA system requires coordination (Vercruysse et al., 2019). Translating climate and complex risk information and research into policy and action has been severely lacking (Klein and Juhola, 2014; Brasseur and Gallardo, 2016; Sillmann et al., 2022) resulting in a ‘operationalisation gap’ between knowledge generation and its uptake in DRM and CCA, as identified within interdisciplinary research projects, e.g. ESPREssO (Zuccaro et al., 2020).

Different stakeholders bring different experiences, and disciplinary expertise from data, models and tools, to governance and communication systems knowledge, providing crucial information for assessment from diverse standpoints, including scientific knowledge and other knowledge systems (Fischhoff, 1995; Daniels et al. 2020; Bharwani et al. 2024). Collating the best available knowledge to manage climate and disaster hazards and risks requires tapping into diverse knowledge repositories across stakeholders (Kelman et al., 2012; Mercer, 2012; Weichselgartner and Pigeon, 2015). Often, climate information and data remain overly technical or are developed in isolation from user needs, which thus reduces its usefulness for, and uptake by, decision-makers (Lemos et al., 2012). Not all knowledge and knowledge types (e.g. local or practitioner as well as scientific) are included as ‘trusted’ knowledge in a particular domain – often as a result of perceptions shaped by (primarily Western) epistemological assumptions (Shawoo and Thornton, 2019; Funk and Guthadjaka, 2020). Creating a shift in the dynamics of power between stakeholders can help build new coalitions and transformative pathways beyond the status-quo (Cosens et al., 2021; Wyborn et al., 2019).

However, disciplinary silos, fractured landscapes of academia, decision-making, practice, financing and policymaking amplify the challenge of collaboration and knowledge exchange. Hence, transdisciplinary collaboration can act as a backbone for DRM and CCA interoperability and integration across organisations, sectors and interfaces cultivating relationships. Streamlining the processes of information and knowledge sharing and synthesising among diverse stakeholders including knowledge producers and users remains a challenge (Dilling and Lemos, 2011; Daniels et al. 2020). Such information silos and discrepancies between actors at different levels are likely to result in oversights, replication and redundancy of communication and information use. A lack of governance processes that identify and address user-needs can propagate the providers development of solutions and products - such as risk models and scenarios - that are not fit for management purpose and decision-making context. Establishing pathways for transdisciplinary collaboration and communication between producers and users of data is essential to develop processes as well as information products that balance model complexity and output granularity to maximize their impact.

Training need:

Knowledge co-production can address the gaps outlined above and support the demand-led tailoring, preparation and provision of ‘usable’ as opposed to just ‘useful’ information (Lemos et al., 2012). Knowledge co-production can enable transdisciplinary collaboration for more effective management of complexity, environmental change, and risk (Cosens et al., 2021; Norstrom et al., 2020; Polk, 2015; Mees et al., 2017; Brugnach and Ozerol, 2019). DIRECTED proposes to address the complex and interconnected challenges of interoperability and integration in data and models, information and communication, and governance, through inclusive transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes. However, as seen in Section 3, there is limited practical and interactive guidance or training available to support practitioners to build their capacity to establish and sustain transdisciplinary collaborations. Such training could guide them to simultaneously understand and navigate their risk contexts, disciplines or relationships with stakeholders involved, to potentially trigger change at an organisational level. As such supporting emerging ‘transdisciplinary’ (Cosens, et al., 2021), boundary-spanning roles (Williams, 2011), collaboration champions (Crosby and Bryson, 2010), and ‘integration’ experts (Hoffmann et al., 2022) helping to bridge practice and science.

DIRECTED sets out plans to train RWL hosts on knowledge co-production and develop learning modules in a Training of the Trainers programme (see D1.2 Capacity Development Strategy for details). Together scientists and practitioners’ skills (e.g. knowledge integration, reflexivity, communication) are expected to develop through the hands-on knowledge co-production implementation process. The Science4Policy Framework developed by the Joint Research Centre outlines a set of competences which are essential to increase the impact of scientific knowledge on policy (Schwendinger et al. 2022) – many of which skills will be targeted through the knowledge co-production training. Taking a broader standpoint beyond the RWL host capacity development, the DIRECTED training (in Task 6.3) can generate guidance for other DRM/ CCA practitioners to learn about knowledge co-production based on the experiences and lessons emerging from the RWLs and DIRECTED consortium. Such training, although targeting practitioners, would also be relevant for scientists/ researchers who are supporting knowledge co-production processes. DIRECTED Deliverable 1.1 provides more insight into how the Real World Labs are setting up their stakeholder engagement and knowledge co-production processes.

4.2 Integrated planning DRM and CCA

The phases of the risk management cycle and climate adaptation are carried out under the direction of various planning departments with different responsibilities. Actor responsibilities are fragmented across multiple institutions, sectors and levels, thus requiring mechanisms to enable integration and interconnectedness across governance systems (Keast et al., 2007; Gilissen et al., 2015; Cumiskey et al., 2019). Resulting from changes in climate, vulnerability and exposure (Merz et al., 2021; Steinhausen et al., 2022) Disaster Risk Management is a continuous task and is closely interconnected with Climate Change Adaptation. There is a lack of knowledge transfer processes that facilitate the application of new knowledge into DRM and CCA policy (Albris et al. 2020) typically hindered by a lack of institutional structures to facilitate this (Amaratunga et al. 2017).

In line with the EU Adaptation Strategy (2021) EU Member States are developing climate risk assessments, National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), regional/local adaptation plans and sectoral adaptation plans, with progress up to 2021 available (European Environment Agency, 2022). The global Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015 – 2030 guides the development of national DRM strategies or plans outlining goals, objectives and associated actions (measures) for reducing disaster risks. While other DRM related plans include flood risk management plans under the European Floods Directive (2007/60/EC, 2007) and National Risk Assessments under the Civil Contingencies EU Civil Protection Mechanism. Associated frameworks and policies do recognize the need for integration across DRM and CCA to capture efficiencies and synergies (Mysiak et al., 2018; Schweizer and Renn, 2019; Medway et al., 2021; Adams et al., 2020; Leitner et al., 2020) but gaps in governance, capacity, communication and data/modelling are hindering efforts to achieve integration across DRM and CCA from national to local levels (Islam et al. 2020). Data and models are usually applied for dedicated tasks in a sectoral approach with limited awareness of where integration is needed. Planners/ managers need to update design values to account for future changes and adapt e.g. structural defences and flood control systems or integrating extreme precipitation and other hydrological variables to future climate conditions for future flood risk assessment and climate adaptation (Byun and Hamlet, 2020; Hattermann et al., 2018). However, these connections are not anchored in planning processes and lack accessible and transparent information on local climate change impacts on hazard variables. Management decisions need to be informed by an understanding of interdependencies across sectors and the potential for maladaptation (Schipper, 2022). Furthermore, selecting parameters for climate, hazard and risk modelling is a subjective (and often political) process. Conceptualizing mapping, and modelling losses and damages with extreme events tend to focus on economic aspects at the expense of impacts in terms of human well-being (McNamara and Jackson, 2019), which then has a knock on effect in terms of planning and resource allocation.

Additionally financial and legal mechanisms and processes including political will and disconnected short-term financing, pose challenges for integrating DRM and CCA planning (Kong et al. 2020; Cumiskey et al. 2020; Dias et al, 2021; Birkmann and Von Teichman, 2010). Based on experiences in the RWLs the civil protection or emergency management actors have

limited engagement with municipal authorities responsible for climate adaptation planning. There is a need to find a common language among the different stakeholders to support integration between DRM/ CCA planning processes and instruments. A lack of clarity on roles and responsibilities and lack of mandate to facilitate integrated planning makes it difficult to create incentives or support for creating spaces for dialogue and discussion across disciplines and sectors. Critical reflection on the societal implications of different DRM/ CCA management options is needed (Schweizer and Renn, 2019). The concerns and value judgements of relevant interest groups and the affected public need to be heard through discourse-based strategies of co-production, inclusion and participation that go beyond consultation (Mees et al. 2017; Schweizer and Renn, 2019).

The Emilia-Romagna RWL (Civil Protection Agency) in Italy identified the need for more ‘what if’ local scenarios to better plan for extreme climate/disaster events together and support communication with local municipalities. Furthermore, the need for including more vulnerability and exposure data within early warning assessments to provide more action orientated information was identified in the RWL. This reflects the shift towards impact-based forecasting and warning, which supports the integration of socio-economic data alongside hazard data for planning and decision-making. The need for an integrated and holistic approach to planning at the river catchment or coastal zone level was highlighted by the Capital Region of Denmark RWL, but a lack of incentives and understanding of the benefits/ trade-offs of taking measures makes this difficult. The lack of legal clarity makes this additionally challenging, for example if one municipality (collecting taxpayers’ money) can legally pay for coastal/ upstream protection in another municipality. In the Danube RWL, the private sector plays an important role, but limited data management capacity in the public sectors makes it hard to capture synergies and collaboration.

Training need:

Despite continued calls for more coherence between DRM and CCA policy and practice, good practice examples of methods, policies and practices capturing synergies are limited (Mysiak et al., 2018; Booth et al., 2020; Deubelli and Mechler, 2021). Through DIRECTED, knowledge co-production processes in the RWLs, supported by the suite of interoperable data/model and tool Use Cases, and the Data Fabric, offer the opportunity to strengthen capacity around integrated DRM/ CCA planning. The transdisciplinary setting in the RWLs will help to deconstruct disciplinary silos using interactive and creative methods, with a commitment to unpacking, explaining, and interpreting field-specific or otherwise highly contextual concepts with actors to support knowledge integration in planning for disaster and climate resilience (Daniels et al., 2020; Andre et al., 2021). Co-production can be leveraged in the efforts to build harmonized language regarding shared challenges and potential management options.

The survey conducted within the consortium highlighted that RWLs require support on planning and policymaking for DRM and CCA. However, RWL hosts’ organisations have varying degrees of power to directly influence planning process, and through the transdisciplinary collaboration and enhanced dialogue in RWLs are expected to identify specific leverage points to support integration for future planning. Lessons from the RWL

knowledge co-production processes and emerging interoperable/ integrated technical and governance solutions will play a central role in informing the training materials developed for inclusion in the e-Learning platform. These applications will be repackaged to help inform and guide other DRM and CCA practitioners working with similar challenges in different settings.

4.3 Citizen engagement and risk communication

Knowledge gap

Communication of climate and disaster risks to the broad public is typically one-way and homogenous e.g. hazard warnings/alerts or risk maps. Building on the challenges above, the multi-level layered nature of governing and communicating risk, result in a lack of clarity and often mismatch between who is producing the most accurate up-to-date risk information and those that have the mandate (and often lack capacity) to disseminate it. Even the most elaborate forecasting models and early warning systems will be rendered ineffective in the absence of timely and clear communication that has not been tailored to users' needs (Lemos et al., 2012; Kreibich et al., 2017; Fakhruddin et al., 2020). Two-way dialogues that identify, engage and consult with specific stakeholder groups to develop tailored communications and three-way participation through collective and continuous processes of knowledge production between citizens, science and decision-makers can bridge this gap (Stewart, 2024). The Societal Resilience Cluster (SRC) developed policy recommendations focusing on improving engagement and strengthening communication among citizens and authorities in DRM (Societal Resilience Cluster, 2023).

RWL experiences recognised the knowledge gap in public risk communication (some RWL experiences). In Emilia-Romagna, Italy, stakeholders see the need for more focus on improving last-mile communication of early warnings to the public (i.e. understanding which channels are effective and used by different groups) – for example to provide tailored information to tourists especially for wildfires. Furthermore, patchy communication flows result in information often arriving late to the municipalities who communicate with the public. In the Rhine-Erft German RWL, the need for understanding and exploring the legal boundaries of what the Erftverband (water board) can and cannot do in terms of public communication was identified. Their locally derived understanding and knowledge based on detailed models can provide more detailed localised information, but there is no guarantee this matches the nationally disseminated warnings, and thus poses a risk in terms of managing their accountability if their released information is dissimilar. The challenge of integrating these informal volunteers into the formal system is recognised in other contexts (Twigg and Mosel, 2017) Furthermore, the challenge to manage spontaneous volunteers during an event was identified by German and Italian RWLs, which although well-intentioned can pose additional risks and needs to be coordinated – a challenge that is evident across other contexts (SRC, 2023). The Danish and German RWL demonstrated the gap in knowledge on how to engage in a supportive way with flood-affected communities and how to communicate the probability of flood occurrence (i.e. return periods) and expected change in frequency due to climate

change. There is often a mismatch between risk perception and action among citizens and civil protection authorities, resulting in misaligned expectations around personal- and authority-led preparedness actions (Vollmer et al. 2024). As highlighted in the SRC policy brief, authorities need targeted risk communication strategies for different audiences and require funding for science communication experts to help authorities to interpret scientific information and help make it understandable and actionable by the public (Societal Resilience Cluster, 2023). The LINKS project (as mentioned in Section 3) developed a [guidebook](#) with concrete steps authorities can integrate into their emergency planning for communicating risks, making information accessible, and mobilising citizens and spontaneous volunteers. Two- and three-way risk communication and co-creation or co-production processes between citizens, civil protection authorities and other risk management and climate adaptation actors is needed to stimulate dialogue, exchange knowledge and bridge the communication gap (Vollmer et. al. 2024, Bharwani et al. 2024)

Training need

The Disaster Resilience Cluster brings together projects producing highly relevant and practical guidance and in some cases training material, that is relevant for supporting risk communication with citizens for multi-risk management and climate adaptation. In the DIRECTED context, RWL practitioners are taking a staged approach to citizen engagement - an approach which is advised by the RiskPACC Framework (see Vollmer et al. 2024). Inclusion and participation of all stakeholder groups, including citizens, is at the heart of the Risk-Tandem Framework, and is expected to support RWLs as the progress on their journey towards more transdisciplinary engagement with citizens. To stimulate thinking around this journey, a [DIRECTED Exchange and Inspire webinar series](#) targeting RWLs was organised with external speakers from projects including RiskPACC. Updates to the Risk-Tandem Framework aim to produce more targeted training and guidance around citizen engagement for authorities and would aim to signpost and build on the guidance and lessons emerging from past and current projects including those in the Disaster Resilience Cluster and others that the project partners are working with e.g. AGORA on citizen science methods (SEI) and REAL DEAL (RIFS) developing a protocol on meaningful citizens' participation. Additionally, possibilities for the Data Fabric to support authorities around citizen engagement will be explored through the project.

4.4 Interoperable information and communication systems

Knowledge gap:

Managing imminent emergency or disaster situations requires complex communication and coordination within and across different organisations. The [international responder forum](#) has identified capability gaps in their work around the integration of information from multiple and non-traditional sources into incident command operations, the need for interoperable communications with responders under any environmental conditions and for actionable intelligence based on data and information from multiple sources (IFAFRI, 2018). Kriebich et al. (2022, 2023) identified that the integration and exchange of data with enhanced accessibility of information was one of the key factors influencing the effective response to flood and drought-paired events.

Interoperability can mean the ability of two systems to communicate with each other or the ability for multiple organizations to work together to exchange information. Looking specifically from a technical perspective on data/models and tools interoperability can be considered “the possibility for spatial data sets to be combined, and for services to interact, without repetitive manual intervention, in such a way that the result is coherent and the added value of the datasets and services is enhanced”, as defined by the INSPIRE Directive (2007). Achieving interoperability across multiple DRM/ CCA organisations’ systems presents challenges including accessibility, comparability, quality, organisation and dissemination of temporal and spatial data for natural hazards (Tomas et al., 2015). Additionally, it is important to understand the underlying (subjective) assumptions, as well as oversights, replication and redundancy of communication and information use due to information silos. Model taxonomies and the key variables, their definitions, and the general approach to their use may not be consistent across institutions or within models in the same field (Barrott et al., 2020), and thus the need to support interoperability and a shared understanding of terminology and language used across different knowledge domains.

In the RWL contexts, interoperability challenges were identified that hinder their capacity to proactively prepare for and respond to natural hazards. For example, in Emilia-Romagna the sensor data for monitoring flash flooding takes too long to arrive in their system because the monitoring networks of different operators are not integrated. During the Flood Exercise event in Rimini June 2024, an interoperability gap was identified in the volunteer information/database whereby they wanted to be able to access more real-time information from the authorities on the impact of the flooding to inform the actions that they can take.

In addition, the fragmented capacities and responsibilities for collecting and recording risk data were highlighted by the Capital Region of Denmark RWL stakeholders. Furthermore, a lack of common hazard/ flood modelling across municipalities and a lack of standardisation, and a reliance on simple existing tools (e.g. Klimatlas instead of more advanced technologies like the DTU Cost Damage Tool) was identified. This highlights how the underlying interoperability

challenges related to data and modelling can cascade into challenges for governance and communication of risks on a catchment or coastal zone level. Within DIRECTED, collaborative efforts aim to create interoperable modelling and data platforms that streamline data collection, analysis, and visualization for organisations working on DRM and CCA.

Training need

Users of information are presented with an overload of information daily, with little guidance on its value, credibility and applicability to their decision context. Taxonomies can be useful in surfacing a shared understanding of how the same terminology may be applied or interpreted slightly differently in practice (Barrott et al., 2020). In describing content online in a standardized way, taxonomies can help tackle both the abundance and fragmentation of information by creating connections, synergies and interoperability across different domains, promoting cross-fertilization and thus reducing silos. An open-source taxonomy (co-developed with RWLs and the modelling teams) enabling external platforms (e.g. the EU CORDIS research results database, PreventionWeb, weADAPT, Climate-ADAPT) to share qualitative data (e.g. lessons learned) seamlessly with the Climate Connectivity Hub, will enhance 'search and discovery', and maximise connections and interoperability between the content (Figure 7).

Figure 7: The Climate Connectivity Hub.

The co-developed taxonomy will enable harmonized language and understanding within the Data Fabric and the potential visualization of a 'glossary' of terms and concepts with

corresponding definitions, synonyms and scope notes to enhance the capacity of modellers and stakeholders to utilize both a shared vocabulary and multiple interpretations of the same terminology (Figure 8).

Any training developed within DIRECTED would aim to support and encourage more standardisation of data and transparent taxonomies. It is expected that through the Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric, DRM/ CCA practitioners can be guided to identify the barriers for interoperable operational systems and identify opportunities to overcome them through technical and/or governance solutions. The Data Fabric can act as the backbone to help guide support more advanced and beginner users to navigate interoperability in different RWL contexts based on their specific information needs for more robust decision-making. Training around interoperability should support enable integrated data and modelling infrastructure can be embedded into institutional systems and result in improved risk analysis, communication and management decisions for DRM and CCA.

Explore

Keyword:

Adaptation

193 articles

10 organisations

1 keyword

Alternate name: Climate change response

Summary:

The process of adjustment to actual or expected climate and its effects. In human systems, adaptation seeks to moderate or avoid harm or exploit beneficial opportunities. In some natural systems, human intervention may facilitate adjustment to expected climate and its effects. ([IPCC AR5 Summary for Policymakers, 2014, p. 5](#) and [IPCC AR5 Technical Summary, 2014, p. 40](#)).

Scope notes:

In the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) process, particularly from around 2008 with the Bali Plan of Action, we see a growing understanding of the necessity for adaptation in face of climate changes we are already committed to. Much of the older terminology and concepts are unchanged in climate change adaptation (CCA), such as incremental adaptation, but in addition a number of newer terms have been adopted such as 'transformational adaptation'. 'Climate resilience' is another newer term which in some circles means the same thing as adaptation. The promotion of resilience "offers the opportunity for more holistic and proactive responses" (O'Brien et al., 2011) based on local knowledge and capacity. United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UN/ISDR) has also adopted the term resilience, describing coping and recovery processes and but also the ability to adapt/change. According to Mitchell and van Aalst (2009) climate change adaptation has much more visibility, funding and political momentum than does disaster reduction, presenting an opportunity for DRR to be linked with the more advanced climate change agenda (having mechanism for international negotiations, having legally binding accord, financing in place etc.).

Adaptation is increasingly discussed in terms of two different but potentially complementary approaches:

- **Incremental adaptation:** Adaptation actions where the central aim is to maintain the essence and integrity of a system or process at a given scale.
- **Transformational adaptation:** Adaptation that changes the fundamental attributes of a system in response to climate and its effects.

Figure 8: An example of a taxonomy concept in the Climate Connectivity Hub with definition, synonyms and scope notes.

4.5 Integrating open source/ access knowledge

Knowledge gap:

In DIRECTED, most data sets have a spatial and temporal reference and follow standards developed by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) that are largely accepted. However, the OGC also offers more than 30 standards for geospatial data and information exchange. Whether the desired data set and the tool to further analyse and process the data are compatible is not guaranteed and often intermediate steps to further transform and map the data are necessary. Licensing terms can restrict the use and sharing of data, while privacy regulations, such as those mandated by the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679), impose additional layers of complexity, often requiring the anonymization of data.

However, there is some uncertainty around the longevity of open data and models which stems from a lack of explicit commitments from the providers to invest time in maintenance and updates. Metadata is key to meaningfully using the acquired data and modelling results in subsequent processing steps. Information about the semantics of the data, its origin and provenance and also normative assumptions need to be understood. This compromises interoperability and the potential for long-term benefits, introducing a risk for users in deciding whether to rely on open data models or not. While this results in a data challenge, it is ultimately a governance and cultural challenge.

Some RWLs, for example, the Capital Region of Denmark identify the limited capacity in municipalities, emergency management agencies to integrate emerging open source data and technologies such as Copernicus satellite data, OGC based services and models hosted on open access repositories to support their work. However, in other RWLs, for example ARPAE in the Emilia-Romagna Region have scientists working with advanced models and tools to support riverine and coastal forecasting to inform early warning and civil protection activities but lack knowledge on preparing for extreme climate scenarios. Generally, the gap is limited guidance on how open source technologies can be made interoperable with existing technology/ data/ models/ tools within and across organisations.

Training need:

Overall, more training is needed to support practitioners including their technical staff (and data stewards) within DRM and CCA organisations to integrate open source and open access data, models and tools.

Technical specialists/ data stewards can benefit from understanding the possibilities of open source data, models and tools and access guidance on how to integrate into operational practices. The training need is especially evident when it comes to the capabilities, use and implementation of open standards such as OGC, and open models accessible via Git repositories. This may also include general information about the software development community and how to productively interact with developers. Training on the operation of newly integrated tools in a productive environment is required and will be provided for selected

models. The need to collate and aggregate such information on open source developments can be met by hosting test setups and interactive documentation on platforms such as [EU Node](#). This can enable users to test models without the need of setting them up in their own systems, aiding them in exploring new developments.

4.6 Multi-risk uncertainty & interpretation

Knowledge gap

A cascade of uncertainties in (multi-)risk models, subsequent coupling and related input- and output- data is a challenge that hinders the integrated decision-making for risk management and climate adaptation. Modelling typically implies certain assumptions on the inputs and the outputs, as well as modelling biases (Wang et al. 2014) and uncertainties (Pianosi et al., 2016; Kropf et al., 2022). Processing through models and chains of models, means that model outputs are used as input to other models, thus the importance of data interoperability (see section 4.4 above). Understanding and communicating how the uncertainties propagate as the network of models grows presents a challenge. The embedded normative assumptions may influence adaptation planning substantially, e.g., economic models respond sharply to growth projections (Buhaug and Vestby, 2019) whereas pathway-based models may streamline conceptual understanding and future planning, and limit focus on the intricacies of uncertainty modelling. Improving transparency and contextualization in how data and models are constructed becomes more important, but remains a challenge because of the proprietary nature of commercial data and model providers (Arribas et al. 2022). The challenge is to provide the appropriate amount and level of data and contextual knowledge sharing necessary to inform the next stages in modelling or decision-making processes that supports integration. An overabundance of detail in data and metadata can obscure vital insights, and a very complex model at one stage may be suboptimal for later applications. Although technical solutions such as the definition of data standards are pre-requisite for achieving interoperability, communication and exchange between experts of connected models and data is often the only way to maximise success.

Local expertise is needed to interpret model outputs and use information to guide DRM and CCA decision-making, such as deciding when to evacuate or distributing resources among climate adaptation strategies. However, these local judgments often hinge on historical data (Šakiic Trogrlić et al., 2019), which may not account for new or evolving risk patterns. Due to their forward-looking nature, uncertainties and biases, subtle or overt, human oversight in interpretation is a necessity. Uncertainty is difficult to accurately predict not only for the occurrence of events but also their potential consequences while ambiguity arises if there are different views on relevance, meaning and implications of the information for decision-making (Aven and Renn, 2020). Again, facilitating knowledge sharing and iterative and reflexive communication among users, data providers, modellers, policymakers and even the general public is needed to support the interpretation and communication of such climate and risk-related data, models and tools. These interactions are important for systematically mitigating

errors that propagate through data and model chains but also for identifying and addressing uncertainties and biases that could affect decision-making based on the data, model outputs and their interpretation. Knowledge co-production process can create open and transdisciplinary collaboration towards addressing the gaps between available information and its use.

Training need

Supporting DRM and CCA practitioners and technical specialists to understand uncertainty in existing data and modelling workflows could be achieved by building standardized and simplified data and model pipelines which encapsulate some of the complexity and allows to easily run separate models addressing the same question. For selected case studies in the RWLs multiple models will be run in parallel to be able to compare results and judge the model spread. This would allow for comparing model outputs of different approaches to build deeper understanding of modelling assumptions and awareness of inherent uncertainties. This aims to build trust in the interpretation of modelling outcomes.

5 Knowledge Transfer Plan

Section 3 highlighted existing opportunities for knowledge transfer through training both online and in-person, while Section 4 demonstrated specific knowledge gaps and training needs which DIRECTED can address through integrated responses to multi-hazard risk and Climate Change Adaptation. Based on insights from RWLs, this section identifies specific end-users to target the knowledge transfer and training activities. Per user-group a knowledge transfer plan (KTP) identifies how training (programmes) will be developed to maximise uptake and application of the project's KER's – Risk-Tandem Framework and Data Fabric (including a suite of data, models and tools). Based on the review of the existing training and insights from the RWLs three priority end-users are identified for the training, 1) DRM/ CCA professionals, 2) Technical specialists or Data Stewards (in DRM/ CCA organisations) and 3) (early career) scientists or researchers (further explained in the following KTP per user-group).

The KTP for each end-user reflects on the messages (or training content), the medium (online/ offline, facilitated/ self-guided), the channel (dissemination/ links with communities) and impact measurement (short-term outputs, medium term outcomes, long-term impact). The training (programmes) will be developed in Task 6.4 with a specific objective of marrying governance frameworks (i.e. Risk-Tandem emerging from WP 3 and WP 4) with innovative technical frameworks (i.e. Data Fabric emerging from WP 2 and WP 5) to help in the development of risk and adaptation solutions. The e-Learning portal (D6.4) will host all the training materials and be available by project Month 45 – which will be openly accessible to any user. The programmes will target learning beyond the lifetime of the project and should support continued use of the developed tools in the RWLs and beyond, by other DRM/ CCA practitioners but also students and researchers. The training programmes will be co-designed with (potential) end-users through workshops (online and in-person) with participants themselves designing, delivering and critiquing method.

The KTP and related impact pathway (measurements) will be monitored via Task 6.5. The short-term outputs will identify what we will deliver, where, when and how it will happen, as well as the targets for numbers to be reached and who we will reach. The medium-term outcomes are the changes or contributions resulting from the knowledge transfer activities e.g. confidence in accessing open data or facilitating co-production workshops. The long-term impact is the changes, benefits or values of the activities or outcome for the beneficiaries, and the consequences of the outcomes (Lima and Bowman, 2022). This will not be possible to capture within the time frame of the project, but the expected long-term impact can be assessed, for example, through evidence of (planned) continuity and use of training programmes (e-Learning) across different organisations. To assess the outcomes and impact of the knowledge transfer and training activities, qualitative data will be collected through surveys and interviews with participants within the timespan of the project. Task 6.5 integrates insights from the development, monitoring and piloting of training (programmes) related to the governance and technical frameworks to identify the capacity/ skills needs to better address

the challenges of integrated responses to risk and adaptation management. This Deliverable 6.9 is due in Month 36 and will therefore focus on learning generated within that period.

5.1 DRM & CCA professionals

End-user:

This user-group including DRM and CCA professionals has varied levels of experience and expertise in different sectoral/ disciplinary areas but lacks knowledge on how governance and technical frameworks come together to support integrated DRM and CCA. This can include managers, coordinators, advisors or similar in regional or local agencies such as municipalities, regional authorities, water boards, civil protection/ emergency management who aim to improve their skills to enable integrated technical and governance solutions. The trainings are aimed at DRM/ CCA practitioners with limited (or varied) technical skills but open to anyone including researchers and industry.

Message (training content):

The training content for DRM/ CCA professionals will focus on the KER as the Risk-Tandem Framework which will use and embed the necessary technical tools for (multi)hazard risk management and climate adaptation to support decision-making. Possible questions that emerged from our analysis of the gap assessment findings, and which the training can address are:

- How can I analyse past disaster events and future climate scenarios for integrated planning among neighbouring municipalities, emergency management agencies and other stakeholders?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of using different approaches to analyse and select different DRM/ CCA measures e.g. Cost-Benefit Analysis?
- How can I identify technical and governance barriers and enablers for integrated and interoperable DRM and CCA using real-life examples from different areas?
- How can I facilitate a transdisciplinary knowledge co-production process as part of my role?
- How can I better understand how to work with uncertainty in data/ modelling to better prepare for an extreme event?

The training will use step-by-step guidance and practical real-world examples based on experiences of integrating DRM and CCA emerging from the RWLs. The Data Fabric and interoperable risk models, data and tools Use Cases can be used as part of the training exercises to highlight past and future event simulations and will include the integration of social and physical data.

Medium:

The training will be available through an online openly accessible webpage in the form of an interactive online guidance with an integrated Learning Management System (e.g. LearnPress). This will help practitioners walk through the steps of the Risk-Tandem Framework with links to examples, materials, demonstrations, and specific training resources. Other user-friendly tools like StoryMaps can be integrated to support visualisation.

An e-Learning module(s) or course(s) will be integrated in the overarching interactive guide, however, these details will be further developed and tested during the co-design phase. To ensure accessibility, the e-Learning course will be openly accessible without a necessary log-in and will be self-paced with an expected duration for completion. This course may not cover training around all the available learning resources but will help signpost the user to more detailed information or learning material (e.g. different training modules on knowledge co-production). The feasibility and budget constraints to prepare and host learning materials in languages other than English, as well as possibilities for certification will be explored in the co-design phase in Task 6.4.

Channel (dissemination):

The e-Learning course will be open-access and be continuously hosted beyond the lifetime of the project on the weADAPT platform. To ensure it reaches a broad range of DRM/ CCA professionals it will be cross-posted on various DRM/ CCA communities including PreventionWeb and the EU DRMKC and shared with specific relevant communities including the MI4Adapt and CMINE. It will also be disseminated via specific national networks in RWL countries and others.

Educational mediums will also be targeted using the materials already developed – for example the EUMA Masters programme¹ which focuses on training DRM and CCA professionals.

Impact-pathway (indicators):

- Short-term outputs: number workshops, and number of DRM/ CCA practitioners involved in co-designing and testing the materials, accessibility/use of learning materials
- Medium-term outcomes: bridging knowledge gaps on integrating DRM and CCA, gaining new skills (technical or governance related), knowledge on working with uncertainty.

Planned activities:

- Dedicated workshops online with training content developers and potential users to implement the KTP with a focus on RWLs (end of 2024/ early 2025).

¹<https://civil-protection-knowledge-network.europa.eu/projects/euma>

- Bilateral engagement with work packages developing the Risk-Tandem Framework and Data Fabric to prepare mock-ups/ demos of the e-Learning course and training materials and gain feedback for the design of the training materials (ongoing).
- In-person workshop to pilot/test the training materials and get feedback from DRM/CCA professionals (e.g. municipalities, civil protection agencies) attending the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference in June 2025.
- Bilateral engagement with [weADAPT](#) for hosting the e-Learning materials and other communities of practice to support dissemination.

5.2 Technical specialist / Data Steward

End-user:

These trainings are aimed at the technical specialists in DRM or CCA organisations (e.g. GIS specialists, data managers, modellers, forecasters). In some cases there may be many technical roles within organisations (e.g. Civil Protection in Emilia-Romagna or ARAPE) or in other cases there are limited staff with technical expertise (e.g. municipalities). Here this role can also be framed as the Data Steward (as referenced in D5.1 in the High-Level design of the Data Fabric). This role is more specific to the users identified in each of the RWLs, as the Data Steward decides access to models, data, and can support future training in their organisations, where this guidance will eventually support users beyond the RWLs.

Message (training content):

The training material will focus on guiding specialists in how to set up and embed the Data Fabric and/or its suite of interoperable multi-risk models, data and tools for climate/ disaster risk assessment and management. Users will be supported to understand the possibilities of the different models and tools. Specific questions of end-users could include:

- How can I create a multi-hazard map or a real-time impact map based on forecast data to support decision-making during an event?
- How can I integrate the Climada tool with my own data and models to assess climate scenarios?
- How can I set up a RIM2D model to compare our existing hydraulic flood model and gain insights to help interpret model results?
- How can I set-up the Data Fabric in our RWL?

Medium:

Specific technical guidebooks (e.g. README's, click throughs) accessible by anyone but targeting technical specialists and designed in a user-friendly digest-able way. This can include examples or simplified versions of the data, models and tools (publicly available) built on learning from the RWLs and would be made available through Jupyter Notebooks.

Additionally tailored hands-on training specifically for RWL technical specialists will be completed to respond to their specific needs and applications of the Data Fabric.

Channel (dissemination):

The availability of the training materials will be disseminated through internal DRM/ CCA organisational networks which would not typically be accessible publicly. A version of this training content would be also made available in networks where more technical specialists interact e.g. OGC forums. Other parts of the training are likely to be using local data and closed (inter)organisational systems and therefore cannot be made fully public but will be available for other users within the organisation.

Impact pathway (indicators)

- Short-term outputs: Number of models/tools covered in the technical guidance; number of tailored training interactions;
- Medium-long term outcomes: continued use of the training guidebooks in RWL organisations (users views on the usefulness / usability of the guides); uptake of the Data Fabric (and associated models/tools) by other organisations/ individuals.

Planned activities

- Deliverable 5.4 in WP 5 will work towards training for technical users of the Data Fabric.
- Deliverable 5.7 will create appropriate guides for different stakeholders to access and use the system (due in Month 30).
- Workshops with Real World Lab hosts based on their requests/ needs and ongoing bilateral support.

5.3 (Early career) researchers and scientists

End-user:

This end-user group including (early career) researchers and scientists is not the primary focus of the end-users expected to benefit from the Risk-Tandem and the Data Fabric. However, we recognise that this group will additionally benefit from the training to inform their research, post-graduate or doctoral studies. As such, this group may have a high level of technical expertise to manage data, modelling and tools for (multi) risk management (e.g. engineering, data science or natural sciences expertise) or governance and communication related expertise to support multi-stakeholder collaboration and decision-making processes (e.g. social sciences, community engagement and planning).

Message (training content):

The training content will vary depending on the specific interest and needs of the researcher. Some researchers or scientists will be able to benefit directly from learning content in the e-Learning module and related guidance and resources on Risk-Tandem (see subsection 5.1). Whereas others will have more interest in technical guidance on the Data Fabric and related tools/ models (see sub-sections 5.2) because they are implementing combinations of tools in their research project e.g. Climada or Rim2D.

Medium:

The training is expected to be delivered through multiple mediums – e-Learning and technical guidance. Additionally, through collaborations with other EU projects we are identifying opportunities to support and engage with early career researchers and professionals for example through conferences, events and summer schools (including connections to relevant Doctoral Training Networks and COST Actions).

Channel (dissemination):

DIRECTED consortium members have opportunities to interact with research students directly through guest lectures and PhD/MSc. supervision. Opportunities to share learning materials and guidance will be utilised there. The consortium will also ensure the training materials are disseminated at related scientific forums, events and conferences e.g. Risk-KAN, European Geosciences Union and Society for Risk Analysis.

Impact pathway (indicators):

- Short-term outputs: number of DRM/CCA professionals and students/ early career researchers attending summer school; number of guest lectures completed using DIRECTED KERs; number of PhD/MSc. students using the training materials (e-Learning and technical guidebooks)
- Medium-term outcomes: Students' motivation and interest in careers in multi-risk management and climate adaptation

Planned activities:

DIRECTED is a partner in organising the Multi-hazard Risk Management Summer School² 22-26 October 2024. The four-day event will bring together around 30 Early-Career Researchers and Practitioners to explore innovative approaches in DRM through interactive and hands-on activities. Other activities like guest lecturing and supporting researchers are expected to emerge as the project progresses.

² <https://www.preventionweb.net/news/multi-hazard-DRM-academy-young-researchers-and-practitioners>

6 Towards Exploitation and Impact

6.1 Training supporting DIRECTED Impact

Horizon Europe uses Impact Pathways to capture and communicate the difference the programme is making on European science, the economy and wider society (Notten et al. 2022). The impact pathway of the DIRECTED project as outlined in the Grant Agreement, seeks to improve the practical management and efficiency of managing DRM and CCA by addressing institutional and practical challenges around decision-making processes, institutional barriers, use of scientific knowledge, increasing capabilities, breaking sectoral/policy silos and improving communication systems.

In summary, the **scientific impact** of the DIRECTED project will assist the scientific community in stocktaking standards for the interoperability of data and models, different phases of DRM/ CCA cycle and across hazards. The DIRECTED project will increase access to actionable science by all levels of governance and society, through for example the production of workflow processes. The **economic impact** contributions include breaking down silos between DRM/ CCA actors to increase work efficiency, streamlining workflows through interoperability, preventing duplication and enabling targeted funding mechanisms, while ultimately reducing the losses from extreme events through enhanced DRM/ CCA actions. The expected future **social impact** of the project includes reduced losses from extreme climate events, stronger provision of scientific outputs and related training by DRM/ CCA actors and responders to better understand the risk and expected impacts and communicate to public actors to enable early action. The overall impact pathway of DIRECTED project including the related outputs and outcomes of the DIRECTED project are outlined in the Grant Agreement.

In the context of this deliverable, here the focus is on the training capacity development impact pathways facilitated through knowledge transfer, rather than impact pathway of the project overall. The achievement of the knowledge transfer related impact will support and feed into the wider project impact achievements.

Table 5. outlines how the knowledge transfer plan is expected to contribute to the outcomes and outputs for the DIRECTED project. In particular Outcome 1 around improved dialogue and cooperation, Outcome 2 around enhanced community engagement, Outcome 5 on new governance strategies and Outcome 6 on multi-risk barriers and enablers, all relating to the knowledge transfer activities and learning resources around Risk-Tandem Framework (KER 1). In addition, Outcome 3 on the innovative use of communication tools, Outcome 4 on the interoperability of tools, and Outcome 7 around cost-benefit analysis of investment and

regulatory strategies, which primarily relate to the training activities and learning resources of the Data Fabric.

Table 5: Expected outcomes and outputs linked to Knowledge Transfer Plan

DIRECTED Outcomes (simplified)	DIRECTED Outputs (simplified)	Knowledge Transfer Plan contribution
Outcome 1 Improved dialogue and cooperation	Output 1 Risk-Tandem use in RWLs	Targeted training and sustained e-Learning materials on Risk-Tandem
Outcome 2 Enhanced community engagement	Output 2 Co-production methodology used by at least 2 municipalities	Targeted training and materials on Risk-Tandem methodology and lessons learned available on e-Learning portal
Outcome 3 Innovative use of media – communication tools and apps	Output 3a Data Fabric used by RWL Output 3b Visualisations of threat/actions in 3 municipalities	Training materials on Data Fabric design, implementation and lessons learned on e-Learning portal
Outcome 4 Overview of existing knowledge/ tools and development of new tools	Output 4 Interoperability of tools used in RWLs to assist decision making	Training materials around interoperability for decision support (Risk-Tandem and Data Fabric)
Outcome 5 New governance strategies and decision making methodologies	Output 5 Governance workflows agreed by stakeholders and implemented in RWL	Exchange of lessons learned around risk governance (Risk-Tandem) and training future DRM/ CCA professionals
Outcome 6 Understanding of enablers and barriers to multi-risk governance	Output 6 Policy brief on risk governance (and uptake by at least one RWL)	Exchange of knowledge on barriers and enablers for risk governance (Risk-Tandem) and interoperability through e-Learning training activities and materials
Outcome 7 Cost benefit analysis of investment and regulatory strategies	Output 7 CBA of DRM/CCA measures made for at least two municipalities (and used in planning or funding applications)	Training and educational activities and materials on cost-benefit analysis and its use in planning/decision making (Risk-Tandem and Data Fabric)

The knowledge transfer plan will also support communication and dissemination activities in the project. Some key cross-project engagement opportunities with potential for collaboration are highlighted in Annex 2. Opportunities include joint training events (e.g. summer schools,

conference sessions, webinars) and knowledge products (e.g. scientific publications or policy briefs) or tools/ data, while ensuring regular updates and exchange to capture emerging opportunities.

6.2 Exploitation / Business development roadmap

Outlining the Knowledge Assets and Tangible Exploitable Products to be exploited under the Business Development Plans.

As explained in Section 1.2, the Knowledge Transfer Plan identifies two Key Exploitable Results for the training activities – the Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric (including the suite of multi-risk models and tools). In the context of the Exploitation Strategy for the DIRECTED Project these are further broken down into three main groups of potentially exploitable products these are:

Knowledge Assets – this includes the **Risk-Tandem Framework** and associated guidelines and courses produced to aid the use of this and other systems within the Project.

The Data Fabric – a tangible exploitable tech system/ service that makes data and information interoperable making the understanding of complex systems possible by all levels of users (from laypeople to expert) – in the case of DIRECTED we are looking at its exploitation within the Disaster Risk Management and Climate Adaptation Sectors – but the Data Fabric has major potential for other sectors utilising complex data systems. The Data Fabric integrates Open Source Solutions and the software developed within DIRECTED will also be published as Open Source Software where applicable, such that the Data Fabric can be deployed and adopted free of charge. A modular design allows to cherry-pick the desired components for the use-case at hand.

The Climate Risk and Adaptation Tools and Models – these are models at different stages of Technical Readiness Levels – some already held within SME's with early market entry commercially and others held within research organisations – therefore the business planning for each of these tools will vary considerably – with the products in the SME's likely to be marketed within the commercial sector within a relatively short period, and the tools held within the research institutes more likely to be used as open access models – nonetheless consideration of how these tools can be utilised and developed long-term, which includes ensuring they are held within institutional spaces that can be utilised regularly with free access, but at the same time ensuring that further financial development can be sourced if their utilisation can be improved.

The tools within this category of exploitable products are listed here in Table 6:

Table 6: Climate Risk and Adaptation Tools and Models under adjustment in the DIRECTED Project.

Tool or model	TRL	Progress on innovations for interoperability	TRL
(a) SaferPLACES Digital Twin Solution for flood risk intelligence (GFZ, GECCO)	7	[Web platform] [Python code] Developing compliancy (API, REST) with RWLs input flood hazard/damage data (forecast and real-time). Output compliancy with Data Fabric and (b), (d), (e).	8
(b) RIMurban pluvial flood risk modelling and forecasting (GFZ)	6	[Numerical model] Added functionality for using additional input data sources, e.g. (c), and for merging model outputs (inundation maps) with data from other sources (remote sensing, VGI), and combining them with vulnerability models.	8
(c) Danube Model (PIK)	3	[Numerical Model] The Danube Model was reactivated with a new CaMa-Flood component, and the spatial discretization was streamlined from irregular subbasins to raster outputs with about four times higher resolution (~5 km with downscaling option to ~90 m).	5
(c) Seamless Forecasting Tool (PIK)	1	[Web platform] The fully implemented Danube Model shall be extended with seamless forecasting capability in a co-design mode with regional end users. For that purpose, a near real-time application has been tested with the Danube model so far.	2
(d) CLIMADA (ETH)	6	[Python code] (probabilistic risk assessment and adaptation option appraisal tool) Adding functionality for multi-criteria inputs and analyses.	8
(e) Damage Cost and Adaptation Model – DCAM (DTU)	6	[QGIS tool] Added input compliancy with hazard data from (a), (b), and (c). Output compliancy with Data Fabric. Alignment with damage cost functions used in CLIMADA. Within the reporting period, the original Danish version of this tool was further mainstreamed and operationalized via the OS2 community of public authorities in Denmark (TRL 8). Explorative work and prototyping, implementing DamageCost damage cost functions into CLIMADA is being carried out at DTU for Central Copenhagen (TRL 5-6). Collection of data from e.g. CLIMADA and SaferPlaces for making the model available at a European level is ongoing.	8
(f) Connectivity Hub (SEI)	1 taxonomy 6 Connectivity Hub	Development of an open-source taxonomy enabling external platforms to share qualitative data (e.g. lessons learned) seamlessly with the Hub (and other platforms/models potentially), to enhance 'search and discovery', and to maximise connections between the content.	6
(g) Oasis-CAIMAN app (OASIS)*	6	Add flood hazard warnings (c), information on how to prepare for a disaster and links to, e.g. (a) and Data Fabric to ensure the wider exploitation of results.	8-9

We will look at each of these exploitable products separately to ensure they reach the proposed TRL level and indeed their paths to TRL 9 – full market integration.

Exploitation Strategy

The DIRECTED exploitation strategy follows a structured process as outlined in Figure 9 below, that takes tangible exploitation opportunities through a process of development over the entirety of the DIRECTED Project and beyond. As this is an innovation project the majority of the tools, models and services have been developed externally to this current project – but the DIRECTED Project assists most of them to define, combine and improve their existing functionality to suit real users, as well as develop interoperability to other models improving the offer of their tools and models. There is one exception to this, the Data Fabric that has been designed to act as the tool that assists interoperability and tailor information to different audience – some as laypersons and others as highly technical audiences. Thus, in essence the business planning allows all the participant organisations with exploitable products, services and knowledge assets to reflect and innovate further their solutions.

Central to DIRECTED, is working on ground-up product development and improvements through the use of one of the exploitation opportunities itself, ‘the Risk-Tandem Framework’, where we work with Real World Lab host organisations to tailor the models and processes under development to the Real World Lab stakeholders’ needs: local municipalities, disaster response and management organisations and in the case of the Danube Region both local disaster management organisations and Insurers.

The diagram below includes the stages of the work, through deliverables that begin the processes of understanding stakeholders (potential users and clients) and improving targeted models and systems (the products) for stakeholder markets.

The DIRECTED Project will be developing appropriate business or exploitation models for each product, service or knowledge asset and later evaluating the potential of expanding the product markets to wider audiences/ markets and sectors. This section outlines the exploitation process and steps we intend to take to enable a full exploitation plan by September, 2026. The plan will enable each beneficiary with exploitable results to have a full road map, actions and new or potential partnerships or commercial vehicles to exploit and scale to their target users and markets by the end of the Project.

It should be clearly stated that the final business/ exploitation plans will be a result of work conducted over the entire project – and not something undertaken in a short period.

Figure 9: Exploitation process and linked deliverables.

Exploitation Process

Market Analysis and Market Proofing

The Real World Lab process lends itself to market analysis through deeply understanding the real world management systems of the partners in disaster management and their on-the-ground processes and problems. Rarely, do organisations developing products and tools get such as immersive experience in the products and tools they are developing.

Detailed understanding will be built up through the project directly through work developed within the deliverables.

WP 1 deliverables: D1.1 Real World Lab Descriptions and problem identification, D1.2 Capacity development strategy for Training of Trainers on implementing transdisciplinary knowledge co-production processes in the RWL and D1.3 Case Study development (in the DIRECTED case - a comparative analysis at local level of major disasters in two RWLs Emilia-Romagna and Rhine-Erft), all assist the market analysis and understanding of the problems that need to be addressed by the RWLs, as well as specific requests from members in the RWLs on how to make improvements in disaster management and climate adaptation moving forward. The results of these deliverables, as well as the planning processes for WP 5 Data Fabric and D4.1 Understanding Information needs, draw out directly from real world partners exactly what they believe is needed to improve the disaster management processes and governance in the future. In turn, the physical and economic tools being used within the Data Fabric will be requested by the Real World Labs to perform tasks requested by the on-the-ground partners, thus once again enabling them to develop an understanding of how potential real world users would seek to use these models and what formats they would wish the information to be delivered in e.g. data, maps and visualisations. In addition, the Data Fabric

will enable a degree of interoperability between the tools thus increasing their functionality and combined results to fulfil user needs.

Wider market analysis will be discussed in the next sub-section, but this phase will occur when we have products and systems tested and developed in live environments that can provide use cases that can be viewed by wider markets and users.

Co-Development and Testing in Live environments through Real World Labs

Once decisions on the requirements for the Labs have been made the Data Fabric and the tools and models will be adapted at the request of the Real World Labs – thus providing the DIRECTED modelling participants and developers with opportunities to use their systems under live conditions as requested by the RWL for disaster risk planning or economic risk assessment. The results will be utilised by the RWL participants themselves and consideration made of the amenity and relative values of the products themselves. Feedback from the RWL's will be useful to help ensure the models and tools are designed appropriately for the target audiences – thus improving and adding value to the initial products. This includes all of the tools, models, the Data Fabric and Risk-Tandem Framework and indeed the training that has been developed. The result of this stage enables the development of use cases that can be utilised for future show cases and broadening the users viewing the products, thus beginning to scale knowledge transfer and the potential exploitation of the products and knowledge assets within new users and markets.

Business Model Development and Go-to-Market Strategies

DIRECTED has a range of organisations who will be considering the best opportunities for their products and services – some of these are fully fledged commercial SME's based around the tools developed, utilised and updated in the DIRECTED Project (e.g. SaferPlaces) and others are held within research organisations and universities (e.g. RIM2D). Therefore, the exploitation phasing will be very different for established SME's, compared to the research institutes within the DIRECTED consortium. Therefore, two main approaches will be taken for exploiting the exploitable products under the DIRECTED Project as broadly outlined in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Two-Tier Business Development Strategies.

Each partner/ IP owner or groups of owners will develop a business plan for their own product or where a product is a combined IP product more than one partner may be involved in developing business plans. The process will involve a gradual process working through each stage at a time, ensuring the product/ service owner has full ownership of their product/ service business plan.

Business Model Canvas and Value Proposition Canvases will be used by each product/ service owner to develop their basis business strategy based on what they have learned during working with the Real World Lab's about their customers and other external work they have conducted with their products and services. Each group will conduct this process through small working groups around the product led by the lead in WP 6 – Tracy Irvine – an experienced entrepreneur and business development professional. These product/ service working groups will then take their models forward and improve them through testing their assumptions with their target audiences. Consideration will also be made to the best way to engage in the exploitation of the products/ services e.g. the products may wish to develop their service into a spin-out company or work with a business or training partner to take the product/ service to market. Likewise, these product/ service working groups will explore the Intellectual Property used with their tools and services and whether they need to get the permission of the IP owners to use their data or knowledge e.g. Risk-Tandem uses a range of frameworks where they will need agreements to full exploit the system. If it is decided there is any IP developed which will need patenting this will be explored during this work.

Discussions with the Real World Labs will also be held to assess whether they would like to continue to use their products/ services and how this could happen – particularly in the private sector applications. Likewise, each group will talk to the wider sector surrounding their

developments and gauge the interest from these organisations to using the products/ services and how.

Other business planning tools may be explored such as market analysis tool, when a team have a range of options but need to explore the potential and priority of markets.

For more developed products with SME's these working groups will conduct a review of their business plans and how the new services can improve their current offer and whether new markets could potentially be considered. For those looking to develop their products further that require future investment from formalised investors – review and work on business summaries and pitch-decks will be developed. If agreed investor meetings may also be set up.

Depending on the product or service a Go-to-Market strategy may also be developed that takes the business planning a step further. This part of the process enables the product owners to establish what they will need to get the product into a fully launched market product or service. Establishing the best ways to market for their products including marketing channels, demand generation, sales strategy, pricing strategy and partnerships.

Other product owners may wish to investigate providing their services as open access/open source, but there will need to be planning on how to sustain these products as open source/ access and indeed continue development in the future. Indeed, open access products still require work on Go-to-Market strategies as the intention is to get these tools fully used and scaled for their greatest impact.

External Innovation Advisory Board

In addition to demonstrations of the different tools and services to new audiences and markets – we will also develop an Innovation Advisory Board. This Board will work to advise our product owners of further steps or opportunities that they should consider, in light of their expert knowledge in the field. The Board will consist of high level stakeholders from policy, government, industry and businesses working in the disaster risk and climate adaptation space. The Board will meet twice, once after the use cases have been developed and our product owners are able to present TRL 7 products and then again, a few months before the end of the project once any advised adjustments and contact follow-ups have been made. Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDA) will need to be signed for products or services that seek to enter the commercial sphere and have unseen Intellectual Property.

The External Innovation Advisory Board will also act as an evaluation body – that evaluates the innovation work that has been conducted and suggests any improvements to the process and plans developed.

On completion of this work each product and service will have a road map/ business plan that has explored their initial assumption, tested them in the real world and improved them as a result, engaged new potential users and markets and developed new partnerships to drive impact. Some of the SME's may also have engaged with new commercial business lines, developed business investment assets and be ready to roll out their products and services in the wider market.

Thus, to summarise the full set of exploitation processes is a full project activity that implements a suite of business planning tools and techniques. The timeline of this activity can be found in Figure 11 Elements of the programme will be completed over time such and will result in tangible results including developed and tested business models, a full understanding of their value propositions to key markets and stakeholders, as well as grounding and the beginnings of market awareness of the exploitable products or services through having established contacts within the relevant sectors. The products will also have been tested in live environments as well as use cases developed to assist long-term market development. It should be clear from the outset that DIRECTED takes the innovation/ exploitation pathway very seriously and intends to take all the products as close to market launch as possible.

Figure 11: Timeline of Exploitation work in the DIRECTED Project.

7 Conclusion

This report outlined the Gaps and Opportunities to support a Knowledge Transfer Plan through training within the DIRECTED project. A review of existing training and education opportunities related to multi-risk management and climate adaptation was completed covering e-Learning courses/ modules, online (interactive) guides, communities of practice (or networks signposting to training), tailored training and paid education/ training courses. Knowledge gaps and training needs were presented that emerged from insights in the Real World Labs and complemented with grey and scientific literature. These included knowledge gaps that bridge technical and governance issues around 1) transdisciplinary collaboration, 2) integrated planning, 3) citizen engagement and risk communication 4) interoperable communication and information systems 5) integrating open source knowledge and 6) (multi)risk model uncertainty and interpretation. Building on these gaps and existing availability of training, the review highlighted the different user-groups and puts forward a plan for training based on the Key Exploitable Results – the Risk-Tandem Framework and the Data Fabric – including the training content (message), mediums and dissemination channel and impact measurement.

These training and education programmes will be co-designed and tested with different end-users within the time frame of the project. The knowledge transfer activities are expected to have a sustained impact, by leaving behind learning resources on an e-Learning portal (D6.4) targeting DRM/ CCA professionals and more technical specialists within their organisations (Data Steward), as well as early career researchers/ scientists to advance their transdisciplinary careers around DRM/ CCA. A legacy document on the capacity and skills development multi-risk management and adaptation will be produced (D6.9) based on learnings from pilot applications of the training.

Overall, the Knowledge Transfer Plan which focuses on training is designed to complement the Capacity Development Strategy (D1.2), Data Fabric related deliverables – Implementation and Interoperability Use Cases (D5.4) and User Training per Role (D5.7), and will amplify the activities in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D6.1) and support the Business Development Plan (D6.5).

Looking ahead to knowledge transfer beyond training, the deliverable presents the steps in an exploitation strategy – in particular for the knowledge assets (Risk-Tandem Framework and associated training), and key exploitable products/ services (i.e. Data Fabric and associated suite of models). The exploitation process moving forward in the project between product owners and potential users in the RWL contexts is outlined including market analysis/ proofing activities, co-development/ testing in real world settings and business model development and go-to-market strategies.

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Annex 1: Survey Questions

Knowledge Transfer: Gaps and Opportunities Assessment (D6.3)

This survey is designed to collect information on the gaps and opportunities in relation to transferring knowledge through training, education and capacity development activities in Directed. The questions cover the following in relation to DRR and CCA within your institutions 1) understanding existing knowledge, skills and attitudes, 2) identifying training activities targeting professionals 3) identifying educational activities targeting students and 4) scoping collaboration with other projects, networks and platforms for knowledge transfer.

The information you provide will form part of the project Deliverable 6.3 Gaps and Opportunities Assessment (due in M9, postponed to M12) and will inform activities D1.2 capacity development strategy (M12), D6.4 e-Learning platform (M45), and D6.5 legacy document on capacity and skills (M36). The information may also be used for conference presentations and/or research publications.

The survey results will be automatically stored in a secured server at University College Cork (in line with GDPR). After the survey is closed, data will be moved to the DIRECTED NextCloud server for analysis (deleted from UCC server). Personal anonymity will be protected, however the data will be attributable to the partner organization to support targeted capacity development.

The survey is expected to take **15-20 minutes** to complete. By completing this survey you are agreeing to participate in this DIRECTED project activity.

The deadline for completing this survey is the 26th of June.

This survey should be completed by all DIRECTED partners. Where deemed appropriate, submissions can be made jointly for organizations by multiple colleagues. Partners are welcome to invite other colleagues within their organization to additionally complete this survey.

If you have any questions please contact Lydia Cumiskey at lcumiskey@ucc.ie.

* Required

Basic information

1. Organisation *

2. Are you completing this survey on behalf of *

- You as an individual DIRECTED project member
- Your organisation (all project members)
- Other

Institutional capacity assessment: knowledge, skills and attitudes

Note: Institution refers to your Directed partner organization. You can answer the following questions by reflecting on the organization as a whole (e.g. university, government agency) or you can answer from the perspective of your closer working group/ colleagues within the organisation (e.g. department, team) that would benefit from knowledge transfer activities through Directed.

Climate Change Adaptation (CCA)
Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR)

3. What is the current level of institutional knowledge and understanding on the following: *

	very low	low	medium	high	very high	Don't know
Discipline specific knowledge (e.g. engineering, planning, science)	<input type="radio"/>					
Interdisciplinary knowledge (DRR, CCA, early warning systems)	<input type="radio"/>					
Models, data and tools (for DRR, CCA, emergency planning)	<input type="radio"/>					
Stakeholder engagement and communication for DRR/CCA	<input type="radio"/>					
Planning and policy making for DRR/ CCA	<input type="radio"/>					
Implementation / operations for DRR/CCA	<input type="radio"/>					
Complex systems/ thinking	<input type="radio"/>					
Integrating knowledge from different disciplines/ stakeholders	<input type="radio"/>					

4. What is the current level of skills in your institution for individuals working on DRR/CCA? *

	very low	low	medium	high	very high	Don't know
Networking	<input type="radio"/>					
Managing challenging conversations (Negotiating/ conflict resolution)	<input type="radio"/>					
Building trust and interpersonal relationships	<input type="radio"/>					
Thinking across disciplines to identify opportunities /gaps	<input type="radio"/>					
Brokering knowledge across different sources	<input type="radio"/>					
Facilitating and convening discussions, workshops and activities	<input type="radio"/>					
Using creativity and innovation to generate new solutions	<input type="radio"/>					
Advocating and engaging strategically with decision-makers	<input type="radio"/>					

5. What is the current attitude and mindset of your institution towards: *

	Very negative	Negative	neutral	Positive	Very positive	Don't know
Benefits of collaboration with multiple stakeholders (government, private sector, academia)	<input type="radio"/>					
Engagement with citizens	<input type="radio"/>					
Change within the organisation	<input type="radio"/>					
Incorporating different knowledges into decision-making (e.g. scientific & local knowledge)	<input type="radio"/>					
Engaged research and/or citizen science	<input type="radio"/>					

6. Who would benefit most from targeted knowledge transfer activities from Directed within or beyond your organization? *

Training opportunities for knowledge transfer targeting DRR/CCA professionals

7. What training and skills development opportunities currently exist in your institution that directly or indirectly support DRR/ CCA? *

- Continual Professional Development training programmes (online or in-person)
- Secondments
- Internships / placements
- Job rotations
- Mentoring
- on-the-job training (project acquisition, event organisation, involvement in multiple projects)
- Attendance at webinars, events, conferences
- Other

8. Please provide more details about the training opportunities listed above which are most relevant for Directed e.g. trainers, duration, delivery mode, accessibility. Please include relevant links.

9. How can Directed best strengthen these existing activities or develop additional training activities targeting DRR/CCA professionals? *

Educational / University knowledge transfer targeting students

10. What education related knowledge transfer opportunities exist in your institution for engaging with students around DRR/CCA? *

- Specific university module content (e.g DRR, urban planning)
- University programmes (bachelor, master)
- Internships
- Thesis topics (focused on practice/policy)
- Summer schools or other focused training/ workshops
- Real world examples, case studies or projects
- Guest lecturing
- PhD topics/ supervision
- Mentoring/ networking
- Student exchanges/ secondments
- MOOC (e-learning)
- Other

11. Please share more details on the specific knowledge transfer activities happening in your organisation e.g. programme title, role, duration. Please include relevant links.

12. How can Directed best strengthen these existing activities or develop additional educational activities? *

13. Does your institution engage in any primary/ secondary school or community related education programmes? Please share any details or suggestions where Directed could support. *

14. For university partners, is your university part of any European University programs? For example, UCC is part of the European University of Post-Industrial Cities (<https://www.unic.eu/en/universities>)

15. What educational ambition(s) do you think Directed should work towards to facilitate knowledge transfer? *

- Designing a MSc. level program via a European University e.g. on Disaster Resilience and building the collaborations to seek funding/ support post-Directed
- Designing a module that could be integrated into an existing University programme and deliver (part of) it during Directed
- Delivering intensive learning programs (e.g. one-week summer school) in collaboration with educators
- Delivering piecewise case studies/ projects/ guest lectures throughout Directed
- Online open module(s) with certificate
- Other|

Collaboration with other projects, networks and platforms for knowledge transfer

16. What other European Union funded projects is your organization working on which are relevant for DRR/CCA and Directed? *

17. What other projects (e.g. local, national, international) is your organisation working on which are relevant for DRR/CCA?

18. How can Directed leverage synergies with these projects esp. in relation to training and education capacity development? e.g. joint summer school, events, secondments, joint publications *

19. What local, national or international networks or platforms is your organization active within that can be used as channels for knowledge transfer and exchange in Directed? *

20. What open-access content/ knowledge hosting platforms does your organization use to access and share open access project information? *

- YouTube
- PreventionWeb
- WeAdapt
- Understanding Risk
- Organisational website
- Other

21. Does your organisation use any e-learning platforms to deliver training and educational programmes e.g. Moodle? If yes, please explain if these would be suitable for Directed to utilise. *

22. Please prioritize the following learning approaches for delivering training and educational content to targeted users within Directed *

23. Please share any other knowledge transfer opportunities/ entry points for Directed that have not been addressed through the above questions?

Follow up

24. Are you willing to have a follow up conversation to discuss the gaps and opportunities shared? *

Yes

No

25. If you answered yes, please share your name and email address to be invited for a follow-up discussion.

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Annex 2: Selected overview of projects with potential for collaboration

Selected overview of collaborations between DIRECTED and other European research and innovation projects and Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs).

Project name	DIRECTED partners involved	Collaboration opportunities
The HuT	Oasis, GECO, ARPAE, GFZ, IIASA, TUBS	Joint work on Emilia-Romagna event analysis and Case Studies Opportunities for knowledge exchange on stakeholder engagement (e.g. case study at Tisza River)
PEERS	TUBS, 52N	Integrating the PEERS knowledge hub with the DIRECTED Data Fabric
C2Impress	TUBS	Cross project workshops
PARATUS	IIASA	Cross project workshops and knowledge exchange on stakeholder engagement (e.g. case study in Bucharest)
MEDiate	IIASA	Cross project workshops/ exchange
I-CISK	GECO, 52N	Knowledge exchange on stakeholder engagement/ user requirement analysis in Emilia-Romagna and Budapest/Zala county
CASCADES	ETH, PIK, SEI	Knowledge exchange on transboundary climate risk in all RWL
Danube4ALL	UCC	Knowledge exchange on Danube region stakeholder engagement
ClimatEurope2	DTU	Participation and joint organization of webinars
UNIC	UCC	City lab in Cork collaboration/ RePIC master learning materials

REACHOUT	UCC	Social vulnerability tool
Myriad	IIASA	Breaking the silos game Knowledge co-development exchange/ lessons Taxonomy development / multi-hazard risk
MAIA	SEI	Taxonomy development / IPCC glossary etc.
AGORA	SEI, IIASA	Knowledge exchange between Italian RWL and pilot regions in AGORA, which focus on citizen engagement
REAL DEAL	RIFS	Knowledge exchange in co-production and policy recommendations

Annex 3: Selected overview of e-Learning platforms considered for DIRECTED

Platform	General Info	Self hosted or not	Costs, licenses
EPALE – electronic platform for adult learning Europe	To publish: fill out form, that will get checked for quality	Hosted by Europa.eu platform	No costs
Capacity4dev	Facilitating collaboration and engagement among peers Enabling cross-learning among practitioners from EU institutions and other organisations Supporting thematic expertise, share lessons learnt and exchange innovative approaches Consolidating knowledge sharing tools and communities of practice in a common environment Improving the efficiency, effectiveness, and quality of EU development cooperation	Hosted by Europa.eu platform	No costs
Udemy	courses can be made available for free courses can consist of multiple chapters containing videos, documents and quizzes	Hosted by you on udemy	No costs, you own the license to what you publish, but Udemy is allowed to use your content for marketing
freshlearn	Helps you to build your own website	Freshlearn hosts the website for you	Free membership with limited tools and features

Classum	Design dynamic learning programs	Classum hosted for you	free version with limited functions (unlimited users)
Trainer central	comprehensive toolkit that includes a website builder, payments system, and multiple options to create online courses	Hosted by Zoho	Free version with limited functions
Gitbook	Qualify for an open-source project to not have to pay money (education-related groups, open-source projects, non-profit organizations) Choose who can access your documentation, centralize knowledge Lots of integrable features (analytics, interactive, support,...) like arcade (interactive product demos)	Hosted on git	Free if you can qualify
Linked in learning	LinkedIn publishes courses to help develop new skills	Hosted on linked in	Prices on demand
Learnpress plugin for WordPress	excellent user interface for online courses creating with any options you need many functions, has technical problems	Needs to be hosted by an external website	Download plugin for free
LifterLMS plugin for WordPress	Create courses from your customizable LMS website	Hosted on your own external website	Free version or by a lifetime license
MasterStudy plugin for wordpress	Create courses easy to use many functions already in free version	Hosted on your own external website	Free version or (much cheaper than LifterLMS) lifetime license
LearnDash	Create courses with quizzes, certificates and assignments many functions, easy to use, flexible	Hosted on your own external website	monthly/yearly payments
Masteriyo	Create courses Unique designs, many fuctions (can be slow sometimes)	Hosted on your own external website	Free version or (much cheaper than LifterLMS) lifetime license
thinkific	Start your products from scratch or use our AI-powered tools to get there faster Focus on creating while thinkific takes care of the heavy lifting — no tech expertise required	Hosted by thinkific	Free version with limited functions
Coursera	Coursera helps you build an online degree program and can provide certificates that can be downloaded to LinkedIn profiles	Hosted on coursera	Price on demand

Partners

